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Informed Consent for Dental Treatment: A Survey on Dental Practitioners' Perception, Awareness and Understanding

MAI Khan¹, A Taleb²

Abstract

A survey was conducted on dental surgeons' perception of ethics concerning informed consent. Forty-six dentists employed in different private and government dental colleges and private dental clinics, responded to a questionnaire, which contained ten questions related to the ethics of informed consent. The study revealed that the dentists were aware of legal and ethical issues related to informed consent, and majority of them relied on verbal consent (82.6%) rather than a written consent for any form of treatment. All the dentists (100%) agreed to the importance of informed consent for patients, and almost all the participants (97%) agreed that patients hold the right to refuse treatment or take legal action if they were not informed properly, although 19% of the participants did not consider failure in obtaining informed consent as an offence. Sixty-three percent of the participants did not agree to the notion that a written consent would make dentistry difficult while the remaining 37% feared that dentistry would be difficult if written consent was made mandatory. The survey also revealed that participants were keen to learn more about principles of medical ethics and felt ethics be taught more elaborately in the undergraduate level. In conclusion it was suggested that dentists should obtain a written consent for ethical reason or legal safeguard or at least keep a written document of the type of consent given by the patient.

Key words: Informed Consent, Bio-medical ethics, Ethics in Dental Practice, Awareness, Perception

Introduction

Ethics is understanding and practicing of moral values and in principle, applies to all the aspects of life. Medical or bio-ethics deal with the moral principles that should guide the members of the medical profession in their dealings with each other, their patients and the state¹. Since The Declaration of Geneva in 1948 and the International Code of Medical Ethics in 1949², medical profession has become more cautious about ethical issues regarding treatment and care. Autonomy or respect, beneficence and justice are the three basic components of bioethics and these three make up the integral part of medical profession⁵. Respect or autonomy means that a patient's judgment should be respected at any level of treatment procedure and he or she has total freedom for taking a decision. Benevolence insures that no harm is done to the patients and the third principle, justice, dictates equal right for each individual. An informed consent, which is supposed to be taken from a patient before any form of treatment, preserves the right of the patient to accept or refuse treatment, insures autonomy for the patient, and in

effect, beneficence and justice by the caregiver⁴. An Informed consent is a cornerstone of doctor-patient relationship. One issue of controversy is promulgating an informed consent in dental practice³.

A conventional consent can take the form of an implied, verbal or a written consent, but an informed consent is one that a patient understands clearly and therefore agrees to accept or refuse a treatment willingly⁶. It is generally accepted that a verbal consent completes the formality of consent for most dental treatment. But an informed consent is associated with both legal and ethical issues⁴. It is generally recommended that a dentist must keep a written account of the type of consent given by the patient and in case of an invasive type of treatment must obtain a written consent⁷. Seear stated that consent in writing has an advantage, for it can more readily be proved⁸ whether a patient has understood a particular treatment procedure and any possible after effect can never be judged by an implied or verbal consent.

The common treatment that the dentists perform at the hospital or clinical settings are dental fillings (with or without local anesthesia), cleaning of teeth or scaling, extraction, root canal treatment and other minor oral surgeries, most of these treatments are noninvasive and low risk, and routinely carried out with or without a written consent relying upon the mostly on implied or verbal consent given by the patient^{12, 13}. Only when a general anesthetic is introduced, a documented informed consent is obtained from the patient as it may

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involve major risks. It is understandable that the majority of the dentists are satisfied with verbal consents from the patients, and the patients are not aware of their right to ask questions¹³. In our country where the dentistry is still a growing area of medical science, the ethics of informed consent is not clearly defined and can be breached with or without the knowledge of the practitioner.

Upholding the code of ethics, a dental surgeon should feel obliged to explain the nature of treatment he or she is going to give to the patient, potential risks related to the treatment procedure, possible alternative to the proposed treatment and the expected prognosis to the patient^{4,8}. In case of an emergency that demands immediate medical attention, the dentist holds the privilege to practice the necessary treatment without the consent of the patient^{6,9}. In case of minor or children below the age of reasoning and also for mentally compromised patients, a legal guardian or a parent with healthy state of mind can give consent on behalf of the patient^{6,10}.

One must understand that treatment without consent is recognized as battery or physical touching without consent. On the other hand, treatment without informed consent is considered as negligence^{3,11}. Failure of the dentist to disclose the risks of treatment can be the basis of a malpractice case. From Medico-legal point, the physician is answerable to the law for failure to obtain an informed consent even for physical examinations¹².

The current survey was conducted using a closed/open-ended questionnaire to understand how the dental surgeons perceive the implications and importance of informed consent in dental practice. The study was conducted as an assignment for Bangladesh Medical Research Council (BMRC), which generously funded the one-month long project.

Methods and Materials

The survey was conducted as an assignment for BMRC, which funded and provided logistics for the study. A questionnaire was prepared asking questions about informed consent and the ethical issues related to informed consent. An explanation and rationale behind the study approach and its objective were briefly described in an introductory letter along with a quotation from a recommended textbook of Dental Jurisprudence so that the participant dentists did not hold any qualms in participating in the study. The participants were assured that the information gathered through this questionnaire would be used only for

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research purpose and this would not be used for any gains from the author's part. It was expected that at least fifty participants could be included in the survey. The participants of this survey were dental surgeons employed in Sapporo Dental College and Hospital, working in different departments of this institution, and dentists working in different private and government health institutions and private dental clinics in Uttara and different parts of Dhaka city. The questionnaire was distributed to fifty active dental surgeons and then the completed questionnaires were collected by the author 3- 8 days after distribution. Most of the answers were expected to be in a simple yes or no, but question no 7 and 9 needed some explanation as it required some level of understanding of the issue in question. The collected questionnaires were then evaluated and the results collated in tabular form.

Results

Out of the fifty-targeted participants, four failed to provide the filled in questionnaires in the specified time. They were omitted from the study. So, a total of (n=46) dentists participated in the survey.

Table 1
Frequency distribution: Gender of dentists

Gender of dentists	Frequency	Percentage
Male	34	73.9
Female	12	26.1
Total	46	100.0

Table 2
Frequency distribution: Educational level of dentists

Educational level of dentists	Frequency	Percentage
BDS	39	84.8
Post Graduate (Diploma/Masters/PhD)	07	15.2
Total	46	100.0

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Table 3
Frequency distribution: Years of dental practice

Years of dental practice	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	36	78.2
6-10	02	4.3
10-20	07	15.2
>20	01	2.3
Total	46	100.0

Table 4
Frequency distribution: Place of employment

Place of employment	Frequency	Percentage
Private Dental College	23	50.0
Govt. Dental Colleges	08	17.4
Private Practice only	15	32.6
Total	46	100.0

Table 5. Frequency distribution: Responses (n=46)

Description of item	Responses	Percentage
Q.01. Mention the principles of ethics, if you are aware of them		
a. Answered	24	52.7
b. Did not answer	22	47.3
Q.02. Do you think it is necessary to take consent before any operative procedure?		
a. Yes	46	100
b. No	00	0
Q.03. Do you keep a record of the type of consent given by the patient?		
a. Yes	11	23.9
b. No	35	76.1
Q.04. What form of consent you take from your patients?		
a. Verbal	38	82.6
b. Written	07	15.2
c. Implied	01	2.2
Q.05. Why do you keep an account of consent		
a. Legal reason	21	45.6
b. Ethical reason	09	19.6
c. Routine procedure	04	8.7
d. Legal + ethical +routine	01	2.1
e. Legal+ ethical	10	21.7
f. Legal+ routine	01	2.1
Q.06. Failure to obtain an informed consent is an offence		
a. Yes	37	80.4
b. No	09	19.5
Q.07. Patient has a right to accept or refuse a treatment		
a. Yes	45	97.8
b. No	01	2.2
Q.08. Patient can take legal action if not informed properly		
a. Yes	45	97.8
b. No	01	2.2
Q.09. Written consent will make dental practice difficult		
a. Yes	17	36.9

Discussion

Results of the study revealed that dentists are more or less aware of the principles of medical ethics, but they are not adequately acquainted with the three words - respect, beneficence and justice, that describe principles of medical ethics, as it is not taught elaborately in the undergraduate level. Most of the dentists expressed their eagerness to learn more about ethics and agreed that ethics be taught more elaborately in their undergraduate level.

The survey found that dentists are aware of legal issues related to informed consent, although the legal side of informed consent is not clearly understood by the dentists, many of the dentists expressed their opinion on the necessity of keeping a record of informed consent for ethical reason. Four of the participants stated that they took informed consent as routine procedure only. It is understandable that from a legal point of view informed consent is necessary and it is also necessary for ethical reason. Keeping an informed consent as a routine procedure can balance both the legal and ethical side of matters.

Out of the 46 participants, only nine (19.5%) shared their view of treatment without informed consent as no offence, although the law states that such action should be categorized as negligence and malpractice⁸. On the other hand almost 97% respondents answered in the affirmative to the question whether the patient can take legal action against a dentist if not informed properly. It is apparent that a patient got upper hand when treated without an informed consent and the dentists are aware of the legal consequences. For two questions, some conflicting views emerged; the first was the dentists are not sure whether they are committing an offence when they are treating without informed consent, on the other hand the same dentists felt that the patients can take legal action if they are not provided with proper information about the nature of treatment.

Almost all the participants (97.8%) agreed to the notion that patients hold the right to accept or refuse a treatment if they are not properly informed about the nature of treatment they are going to receive. A patient holds the right to know what is being done to him, what might be the treatment outcome or major risks related to the treatment procedure or are there any better or less expensive options than the suggested one. So patients have the upper hand in deciding about their treatment modes, and if not informed properly can even take legal action for malpractice or negligence.

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Seventeen of the 46 participants feared that dentistry would be difficult if written consent is made mandatory for any form of dental treatment. Participants opined that low literacy rate and poor socioeconomic status of the population of Bangladesh, could complicate the practice of written consent for dental treatment. The other reasons cited behind their opinions were:-

- Misinterpretation of law by the patient/ legal advisors might compromise the position of the dentist in deciding treatment procedure.
- Take advantage of legal vulnerability.
- Extreme caution during treatment can become time consuming and this may complicate treatment procedure and
- Patients might get frightened if written consent was taken for simple treatment procedure

All the participants (100%) stated the necessity of informed consent for treatment purposes. Majority (76.8%) of the dental practitioners in the survey acknowledged that they did not keep a record of the type of consent obtained from the patient and only a few (15.2%) obtained written consent from the patients, but the majority were satisfied with verbal consent. One of the participants relied on implied consent only.

Of the 46 participants in this survey, most of them are in dental practice for the past five years (78.2%), and one but the rest are with dental practice for at least twenty years. The sample was too small to make an association between experience and awareness level, but it can be assumed that the experienced dentists have learned more about ethics from their professional practice, while the young dentists are equipped with more recent knowledge about law and ethics related to dental science. A similar research conducted in Australia on ethical dilemma confronting dental ethics found that the dentists learn ethics from their colleagues, family, and friends or even from special courses on ethics¹³.

Limitations of the study

The main limitation of the study was small number of subjects involved in the study. So further study on the same topic is proposed with larger number of study subjects and another study regarding the awareness level of patients can be done in the future.

Conclusion

The current survey has revealed that majority of the participating dentists are aware of their duty and obligation to the patients and they agree to the concept of obtaining informed consent from the patients. The

survey findings demand that the dentists need to be serious about dental ethics in their practice, and more they are exposed to moral issues, more they would be aware of the need for good clinical practice.

In the perspective of Bangladesh, where majority of the people are not adequately literate, they can be easily convinced, on the other hand a dental surgeon may not feel obliged to take a verbal or written consent thinking that a patient may not understand its importance, but as per demand of ethics, it is the duty of the dental care giver to aware the patient about his or her right of making decisions regarding treatment. The ethical issues regarding consent in dental practice may or may not have direct effect on the treatment outcome, nor would it make the practice of dentistry difficult for the clinicians. Yet the implications of keeping a record for all types of treatments provided might have some good effect on the present status of dentistry.

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The Proportions of Periodontal Diseases among Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients Attending at the National Healthcare Network (NHN), Mirpur Centre, Dhaka

SZ Mahmud¹, SM Alif², MA Tarafder³, SM Hossain⁴

Abstract

This cross sectional study was conducted to find out the proportions of periodontal diseases among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients attending at the National Healthcare Network (NHN), Mirpur centre, Dhaka using a pre-tested semi-structured questionnaire. The sample size was 120 patients. The mean age of the patients was 46.95±10.31. Proportion of periodontitis was the highest 56% followed by gingivitis 32.5%, periodontitis with endodontic lesions 5%, necrotizing periodontal diseases 4.2% and periodontal abscesses 2.5%. A highly significant association was found between education and knowledge about cleaning teeth before going to bed and after breakfast (p=0.000). More than half of the patients (55%) applied improper technique or method of tooth brushing followed by 39.2% who applied mixed technique and the rest 5.8% applied proper technique respectively. There was no significant relationship between current smokers and periodontal diseases, chewing betel leaf was significantly associated with occurrence of periodontal diseases (p=0.048). These periodontal diseases are multi-factorial and the factors responsible for these diseases are preventable.

Key words: Diabetes mellitus, glycosylated hemoglobin, oral hygiene, periodontal diseases, periodontal pocket

Introduction

The oral cavity provides a continuous source of infectious agents, and its condition often reflects progression of systemic pathologies. Historically, oral infections are thought to be localized to the oral cavity except in case of some associated syndromes and untreated odontogenic abscesses. A change in paradigm has dispelled this notion, and a whole new concept of the status of the oral cavity and its impact on systemic health and disease has been evolved.¹ Systemic diseases and hormonal changes have implicated as complicating factors for periodontal diseases. Gingivitis and periodontitis are sometimes the first evidence that a

patient has diabetes. Given that diabetes may be present for a number of years before it is diagnosed, dentists may be the first health professional to detect patients with diabetes.² Diabetes mellitus and periodontal diseases are two common chronic diseases that have long been considered to be biologically linked.³ The term periodontal diseases usually refers only to plaque related inflammatory diseases of the dental supporting tissues.⁴ Diabetes mellitus (DM) is becoming a pandemic worldwide.¹¹ The prevalence of DM for all age groups worldwide was estimated to be 2.8% in 2000 and an anticipated 4.4% in 2030. The total number of people in the world with diabetes is projected to rise from 171 million in 2000 to 366 million in 2030.¹² This has been estimated to increase to 333 million, or 6.3% of the world population in the year 2025.¹³ Patients with uncontrolled diabetes specially type-2 have poor resistance to infection with effects in mouth cavity and elsewhere in the body, show an unusually high susceptibility to periodontal diseases and increased susceptibility to acute lateral periodontal abscesses.¹⁷ Periodontal diseases have been reported as the sixth complication of diabetes, along with neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy, altered wound healing and macrovascular diseases.¹ The relationship between oral diseases and type 2 diabetes has become a recent focus of attention among healthcare professionals because of substantial evidence supporting the role of diabetes and poor glycemic control as important risk factor for periodontal diseases.¹⁹ In Bangladesh a few studies have been conducted to observe the relationship and factors associated with periodontal disease patients.^{23,25,26} But a few studies have been conducted among the diabetic

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patients. This small scale study attempted to find out the proportions of periodontal diseases among type 2 diabetic patients. **Materials and Methods**

This cross sectional study was conducted to assess the proportions of periodontal diseases among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients attending at the National Healthcare Network (NHN), Mirpur Centre (An Institute of Diabetic Association of Bangladesh), Dhaka. The study was carried out among 120 type 2 diabetic patients who have been suffering from different periodontal diseases and attended this centre for routine checkup. To get the target sample quickly purposive sampling technique was followed by using a pre-tested semi-structured questionnaire and a check list.

Inclusion criteria were: (1) patients aged more than 35 years diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus, (2) patients having glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels equal to or more than 7.0%. Exclusion criteria were: (1) patients who refused to give consent after having been informed about the purpose of the study, (2) patients with co-morbid psychiatric conditions (i.e., drug abuse, suicidal ideation, and psychosis) and (3) handicapped patients.

The severity of periodontitis was assessed clinically by measuring the depth of periodontal pocket using periodontal probe graduated in millimeters was passed through the pocket up to the bottom. Probe was placed parallel to the long axis of individual tooth at six sites and the depth of the periodontal pocket was taken. Pressure during probing was exerted within the range of 20-25 gm. Periodontal index was followed according to Ramfjord (1967) whilst assessment of gingivitis was done according to Loe and Silness index (1967).

Data were checked, cleaned and edited properly before analysis. The data were analyzed by using the software SPSS (Chicago), version 11.5. Descriptive statistics were used for interpretation of the findings. Associations were made by using the Chi square test ².

Results

The socio-eco-demographic characteristics of patients are shown in Table 1. Maximum 34.2% were in age group 36 to 45 years and minimum 7.5% were in age group more than 65 years, 60.8% were female and 39.2% male. The overwhelming majority 90.8% were Muslims followed by 5.8% Hindus, 2.5% Christians and the rest 0.8% were Buddhists. The highest 45% patients' family income was in between 16 to 20 thousand BDT per month and the lowest 4.1% had more than 30 thousand BDT. About 25% patients were illiterate and 21.7% were graduates. In addition, patients age, religion and educational level were significantly associated with

periodontal diseases. Maximum 45.8% were housewives and minimum 1.7% were farmers. Majority of the patients (64.2%) live in urban followed by 14.2% in rural areas, 13.3% in slum and 8.3% in sub-urban areas respectively. There is significant association between age and periodontal diseases (p-value=0.004), religion and periodontal diseases (p-value=0.009), education and periodontal diseases (p-value=0.039).

Table 1: Distribution of the patients according to socio-demographic characteristics and its association with

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	p-value
Age			
<15	16	13.3	0.004
16-45	41	34.2	
46-55	34	28.3	
56-65	20	16.7	
>65	9	7.5	
Sex			
Male	47	39.2	0.430
Female	73	60.8	
Religion			
Muslim	109	90.8	0.009
Hindu	7	5.8	
Christian	3	2.5	
Buddha	1	0.8	
Family Income (BDT)			
10000-15000	27	22.5	0.251
16000-20000	54	45.0	
21000-25000	24	20.0	
26000-30000	10	8.3	
>30000	5	4.1	
Education			
Illiterate	30	25.0	0.039
Primary	18	15.0	
Secondary	16	13.3	
SSC or equivalent	17	14.2	
HSC or equivalent	13	10.8	
Graduation	26	21.7	
Occupation			
Service holder	41	34.2	0.765
Businessman	10	8.3	
Farmer	2	1.7	
Labour	12	10.0	
House wife	55	45.8	
Residency			
Urban	77	64.2	0.250
Rural	17	14.2	
Suburban	19	8.3	
Slum	16	13.3	

periodontal diseases (n=120)

The distribution of the patients according to oral health related knowledge, oral hygiene related behavior and tobacco related habit variables, in relation to periodontal diseases is shown in Table 2. Here about three-fourths majority (71.7%) of the patients had gum problem or gum infection and 32.5% required adult teeth extraction or lost their tooth due to gum infection or tooth mobility. More than half (55%) of the patients applied improper technique or method of tooth brushing. More than three-fourths (77.5%) of the patients never received any periodontal treatment. Moreover, maximum 84.2% of them never visited any dentist for oral and dental check up, 22.5% were current smokers and 31.7% always chewed betel leaf. Gum infection, history of tooth loss due to tooth mobility, regular oral and dental check up and frequency of visit of a dentist are

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statistically highly significant association with periodontal diseases (p=0.000).

Table 2: Distribution of the patients according to oral health related knowledge, oral hygiene related behavior

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	p-value
Gum diseases			
No	34	28.3	0.000
Yes	86	71.7	
History of extraction or tooth loss due to gum infection or tooth mobility			
No	81	67.5	0.000
Yes	39	32.5	
Method of tooth brushing			
Proper technique	7	5.8	0.013
Improper technique	66	55.0	
Mixed technique	47	39.2	
Any periodontal treatment received			
No	93	77.5	0.112
Yes	27	22.5	
Regular oral & dental check up by a dentist			
No	101	84.2	0.000
Yes	19	15.8	
Frequency of visit of a dentist			
6 month interval	12	10.0	0.000
1 year interval	5	4.2	
>1 year interval	2	1.7	
Never visited before	101	84.2	
Current smoker			
No	93	77.5	0.598
Yes	27	22.5	
Chewing betel leaf (Pan)			
No	82	68.3	0.048
Yes	38	31.7	

and its association with periodontal diseases (n=120)

The distribution of the patients according to the proportion of periodontal diseases is shown in Table 3. Proportion of periodontitis was the highest 55.8% followed by gingivitis 32.5%, periodontitis with endodontic lesion 5% and necrotizing periodontal diseases 4.2% whereas periodontal abscesses was the lowest 2.5%.

Table 3: Distribution of the patients by the pattern of

Pattern of periodontal diseases	Frequency	Percentage
Gingivitis	38	32.5
Periodontitis	68	55.8
Necrotizing periodontal diseases	5	4.2
Periodontal abscesses	3	2.5
Periodontitis with endodontic lesion	6	5.0
Total	120	100.0

periodontal diseases (n=120)

The distribution of the patients according to criteria of gingivitis is shown in Table 4. About 57.9% of them suffered from moderate gingivitis followed by 39.5% from mild

Table 4: Distribution of the patients by criteria of gingivitis (n=38)

Criteria of gingivitis	Frequency	Percentage
Mild gingivitis	15	39.5
Moderate gingivitis	22	57.9
Severe gingivitis	1	2.6
Total	38	100.0

The distribution of the patients according to criteria of periodontitis is shown in Table 5. Approximately, 38.2% suffered from marginal periodontitis followed by 30.9% suffered both from moderate periodontitis as well as severe periodontitis.

Table 5: Distribution of the patients by criteria of periodontitis (n=68)

Criteria of periodontitis	Frequency	Percentage
Marginal periodontitis	26	38.2
Moderate periodontitis	21	30.9
Severe periodontitis	21	30.9
Total	68	100.0

gingivitis and 2.6% from severe gingivitis respectively.

Discussion

This cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the proportions of periodontal diseases among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients, 60.8% were female while 39.2% were male. To minimize bias due to misclassification of diabetes type, this study included only those subjects 35 years of age and older because it is recognized that over 95% of individuals with diabetes are 35 years of age and older have type 2 diabetes mellitus. In 2002, one of the population-based survey in the US adult population showed that type 2 diabetes occurs mainly in people aged over 40 years, although it is affecting a large number of young people.¹² The current study also depicted that 34.2% of the patients were from age group 36 to 45 years followed by 28.3% from age group 46 to 55 years. Moreover, there was statistically significant association between age of the patients and periodontal diseases (p=0.004). In addition, mean age and mean monthly family income of the patients were 47±10.31 years and 18200 ±10899.74 BDT (Mean ± SD) respectively. Several studies highlighted the relationship between periodontal diseases.^{23,29} Current evidence also emphasized highly significant relationship between gum problem of the patients and periodontal diseases (p=0.000). In the present study 37.5% of the patients required adult teeth extraction or lost their teeth due to gum infection or tooth mobility. Also there was a highly

Conclusion

In the light to the findings of the present study and discussion thereof, it can be concluded that diabetes is associated with a greater likelihood of developing certain periodontal diseases which result from opportunistic infections, poor glycemic control and lack of information about oral diseases. Of the opportunistic infections, periodontitis and gingivitis are commonly encountered. Education and knowledge of diabetic patients are very important to prevent periodontal and oral diseases. The treatment of periodontal diseases such as scaling, root planning, curettage of pocket etc. as well as other periodontal surgery is a way to control periodontal infections which lead to reduce blood sugar levels in type 2 diabetes and control of diabetes is another way to remain free from the suspicion whenever their patients come with such kind of periodontal diseases.

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Status of Learning Communication Skills in Undergraduate Medical Education According to Intern's View.

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Abstract

This cross sectional descriptive study was carried out during July 2010 to June 2011 in four medical college of Dhaka city. Two government and two private medical colleges were selected according to the convenience of the researcher. One semi structured questionnaire was used to collect the information from the Intern doctors. It contained 26 questions from the variables of communication skills. The researcher himself collected the data. 218 Intern doctors returned the filled in questionnaires on the same day. Allocation of score for response of each item was based on 5 point Likert scale. The study revealed that most of the interns were not taught communication skills in their clinical classes in a structured way. But during internship period they felt that those should have been taught in a structured way. They recommended that it should be a part of course curriculum so that every student gets equal opportunity to learn these skills.

Key words: Learning, communication skill, intern

Introduction

The communication that takes place between doctor and patient provides the foundation for diagnosis and treatment, whatever the branch of clinical medicine¹. Increasing number of medical schools have included brief training course in communication skills. While there is evidence that such a course does improve student's skill². It has become increasingly clear that how doctor communicates with the patients affect the accuracy of diagnosis, compliance, satisfaction and response to investigation and treatment³.

Generally studies have clearly established that students given specialized skills training shows significantly improved interpersonal skill over traditionally trained counterparts. Trained doctors are more able to communicate warmth and understanding to patients and are more able for detecting and responding appropriately to patient's verbal and non verbal cues^{4,5,6}. So it has been observed that communication skill development is very much important in medical education⁵. To produce graduates with a range of

communication skills and attributes Liverpool University introduced communication skill learning course throughout five years. The result of the course showed that communication skills training can produce good and competent communicators⁷. In a study it was observed that student's in the trained group showed greatly increased skills in interviewing and building interpersonal relationship as a result of their communication skill training. The students were significantly better at eliciting full, relevant data from patients, they were diagnostically more efficient, but they took no longer time than their control group counterparts to elicit the information⁸. In our under graduate curriculum there are four weeks' period of communication learning skill in community medicine⁹. In informal way there is scope for learning communication skill in clinical classes by 'history taking', by observing seniors' communication with the patient, taking consent, interpretation of result of investigation or breaking bad news to relatives of the patient by the senior doctors.

Methodology:

This was a cross sectional descriptive study carried out during July 2010 to June 2011. Voluntary respondents of 218 Intern doctors of selected four medical colleges constituted the sample. Two government and two private medical colleges were selected as per the convenience of the researcher. The researcher collected information from the interns as per the following criteria:

" At least ten intern doctors from any of the clinical subjects (medicine, surgery, gynecology, and sub specialties) of each medical college.

" At least 5 teachers from any of the clinical subjects of each medical college.

Research Instrument

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One questionnaire was structured with a space for comment of respondents was used to collect the information from the Intern doctors. It contained 26 questions from the variables of communication skills. The researcher himself collected the data. With prior permission of the authority, Intern doctors returned the filled in questionnaires on the same day. Allocation of score for response of each item was based on 5 point Likert scale.

Data processing and analysis

Data were checked and edited after collection, processed and analyzed by using SPSS software package. Data were presented in the form of tables to compare the findings.

Results

Allocation of score for response of each item was based on 5 point Likert scale. Total respondents were 218 intern doctors. The answer of the intern doctors obtained from the structured questionnaires are shown in the tables.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents as per their

Name of the Institute	Frequency	Percent
Dhaka National Medical College	53	24.3
Dhaka Medical College	63	28.9
Sir Salimullah Medical College	71	32.6
Holy Family Red Crescent Medical College	31	14.2
Total	218	100.0

institutions

Table 2 : Distribution of respondents as per their opinions regarding of teaching learning how to greet the patient , Rapport building of the patient, taking informed consent of patient before performing physical

Different events of Communication skill teaching learning in undergraduate medical education	Different levels of opinion					Total
	Strongly disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Undecided (U)	Agree (A)	Strongly agree (SA)	
"Teacher taught student's clinical class how to greet the patient before history taking"	4 (1.8%)	6 (2.8%)	9 (4.1%)	107 (49.1%)	92 (42.2%)	218
"Teacher should taught student's how to greet the patient before history taking"	2 (0.9%)	00 (0%)	4 (1.8%)	57 (26.1%)	155 (71.1%)	218
"Teachers taught student's about rapport building (gaining faith) of the patient, before dealing with them"	5 (2.3%)	18 (8.3%)	18 (8.3%)	111 (50.9%)	66 (30.3%)	218
"Rapport building (gaining faith) of the patient, before dealing with them should be taught in the clinical class"	1 (0.5%)	13 (6.0%)	8 (3.7%)	79 (36.2%)	117 (53.7%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how to take informed consent of patient before performing physical examination"	1 (0.5%)	4 (1.8%)	7 (3.2%)	98 (45.0%)	108 (49.5%)	218
"Teachers should taught student's how to take informed consent before perform physical examination"	0 (0%)	8 (3.7%)	18 (8.3%)	65 (29.8%)	127 (58.3%)	218

nature of the disease and informing the treatment plan, in the clinical class.

Table 5 : Distribution of respondents as per their opinions regarding of teaching learning how to Break

Different events of Communication skill teaching learning in undergraduate medical education	Different levels of opinion					Total
	Strongly disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Undecided (U)	Agree (A)	Strongly agree (SA)	
"Teachers taught student's how to break the bad news to the patient and their guardian about the disease"	10 (4.6%)	42 (19.3%)	38 (17.4%)	79 (36.2%)	49 (22.5%)	218
"Teachers should taught students in clinical class, how to break the bad news to the patient and their guardian about the disease"	12 (5.5%)	14 (6.4%)	26 (11.9%)	63 (28.9%)	103 (47.2%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how a difficult situation can be managed"	10 (4.6%)	39 (17.9%)	42 (19.3%)	75 (34.4%)	52 (23.9%)	218
"Teachers should students study in clinical class, how they will handle a difficult situation"	3 (1.3%)	7 (3.2%)	29 (13.3%)	72 (33.0%)	107 (49.1%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how they will convince and refer the patient to another hospital for better management"	1 (0.5%)	4 (1.8%)	31 (14.2%)	98 (45.0%)	53 (24.3%)	218
"Teachers should taught how the student will convince and refer the patient to another hospital for better management"	11 (5%)	21 (9.5%)	13 (6%)	68 (31.2%)	105 (48.2%)	218

the bad news, handle the difficult situation and refer the patient , in the clinical class.

In the questionnaire for the interns a space was kept for comment. Only 32 of them gave opinions. The most common opinion was that communication skills should be taught in clinical class methodically and must be assessed in examination. One comment was "Teachers taught us" communication skill (CS) in the way of gossiping or sometimes when any occurrence happened. So some of us could it learn and others missed it. It should be taught in a structured way so that all students can learn. Another interesting comment was "Few teachers taught us but we were not told about it's importance or future application in practical life. So teaching not retain in our memory for a long time. Another common comment was that this study is very good if communication skills teaching is included in the curriculum. This will definitely help in reducing doctor patient chaotic relation in our country. A comment was "You are doing a very good study. If authority includes this in the MBBS curriculum it will help doctors to build good relationship with the patient". In another comment some respondents thanked the researcher for taking their opinions and a few of them thanked him for choosing these burning issues."

Discussion

This study was carried out among the Intern doctors of

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examination, in the clinical class.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents as per their opinions regarding of teaching learning how to convince the patient, to do investigation , describe

Different events of Communication skill teaching learning in undergraduate medical education	Different levels of opinion					Total
	Strongly disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Undecided (U)	Agree (A)	Strongly agree (SA)	
"Teachers taught student's how to explain patient and their guardian about the nature of the disease"	5 (2.3%)	21 (9.6%)	25 (11.5%)	104 (47.7%)	63 (28.9%)	218
"Teachers should taught 's how to explain patient and their guardian about the nature of the disease"	9 (4.1%)	15 (6.9%)	23 (10.6%)	75 (34.4%)	96 (44.4%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how to convince to do the necessary investigations to patient and their guardian"	7 (3.2%)	37 (17%)	15 (6.9%)	110 (50.5%)	49 (22.5%)	218
"Teachers should taught the student the way to convince patient and guardian to do the necessary investigations"	4 (1.8%)	27 (12.4%)	25 (11.5%)	77 (35.3%)	85 (39%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how to Explain patient and their guardian about the treatment plan"	10 (4.6%)	35 (16.1%)	34 (15.6%)	91 (41.7%)	48 (22%)	218
"Teachers should taught student's how to Explain patient and their guardian about the treatment plan to patient and their guardian"	11 (5.0%)	21 (9.6%)	24 (11.0%)	73 (33.5%)	89 (40.8%)	218

Table 4 : Distribution of respondents as per their opinions regarding of teaching learning how to motivate the patient, to receive treatment , convince for painful procedure and counseling about the life style and diet, in the clinical class.

Different events of Communication skill teaching learning in undergraduate medical education	Different levels of opinion					Total
	Strongly disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Undecided (U)	Agree (A)	Strongly agree (SA)	
"Teachers taught student's how to motivate the undecided patient and guardian to receive proper treatment"	10 (4.6%)	36 (16.5%)	33 (15.1%)	74 (33.9%)	65 (29.8%)	218
"Teachers should taught student's how to motivate the undecided patient and guardian to receive treatment"	10 (4.6%)	2 (0.9%)	24 (11.0%)	95 (43.6%)	87 (39.9%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how to convince the patient and guardian for a painful procedure"	13 (6.0%)	39 (17.9%)	40 (18.3%)	96 (44.0%)	30 (13.8%)	218
"Teachers should taught student's how to convince the patient and their guardian for a painful procedure"	14 (6.4%)	12 (5.5%)	27 (12.4%)	64 (29.4%)	101 (46.3%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how to counsel the patient about life style and Diet after hospital leaving"	3 (1.3%)	17 (7.8%)	29 (13.3%)	113 (51.8%)	52 (23.9%)	218
"Teachers should taught student's how to counselling the patient and their guardian about patient's life style and Diet after hospital leaving"	5 (2.3%)	16 (7.3%)	21 (9.6%)	81 (37.2%)	95 (43.6%)	218

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nature of the disease and informing the treatment plan, in the clinical class.

Table 5 : Distribution of respondents as per their opinions regarding of teaching learning how to Break

Different events of Communication skill teaching learning in undergraduate medical education	Different levels of opinion					Total
	Strongly disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Undecided (U)	Agree (A)	Strongly agree (SA)	
"Teachers taught student's how to break the bad news to the patient and their guardian about the disease"	10 (4.6%)	42 (19.3%)	38 (17.4%)	79 (36.2%)	49 (22.5%)	218
"Teachers should taught students in clinical class, how to break the bad news to the patient and their guardian about the disease"	12 (5.5%)	14 (6.4%)	26 (11.9%)	63 (28.9%)	103 (47.2%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how a difficult situation can be managed"	10 (4.6%)	39 (17.9%)	42 (19.3%)	75 (34.4%)	52 (23.9%)	218
"Teachers should students study in clinical class, how they will handle a difficult situation"	3 (1.3%)	7 (3.2%)	29 (13.3%)	72 (33.0%)	107 (49.1%)	218
"Teachers taught student's how they will convince and refer the patient to another hospital for better management"	1 (0.5%)	4 (1.8%)	31 (14.2%)	98 (45.0%)	53 (24.3%)	218
"Teachers should taught how the student will convince and refer the patient to another hospital for better management"	11 (5%)	21 (9.5%)	13 (6%)	68 (31.2%)	105 (48.2%)	218

the bad news, handle the difficult situation and refer the patient , in the clinical class.

In the questionnaire for the interns a space was kept for comment. Only 32 of them gave opinions. The most common opinion was that communication skills should be taught in clinical class methodically and must be assessed in examination. One comment was "Teachers taught us" communication skill (CS) in the way of gossiping or sometimes when any occurrence happened. So some of us could it learn and others missed it. It should be taught in a structured way so that all students can learn. Another interesting comment was "Few teachers taught us but we were not told about it's importance or future application in practical life. So teaching not retain in our memory for a long time. Another common comment was that this study is very good if communication skills teaching is included in the curriculum. This will definitely help in reducing doctor patient chaotic relation in our country. A comment was "You are doing a very good study. If authority includes this in the MBBS curriculum it will help doctors to build good relationship with the patient". In another comment some respondents thanked the researcher for taking their opinions and a few of them thanked him for choosing these burning issues."

Discussion

This study was carried out among the Intern doctors of

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two government and two non government medical colleges of Dhaka city. Selected variables of communication skills were used in this study. Aspergen et al used similar seven main variables in their study to assess the need of communication skills teaching¹¹.

Hargie et al used different types (Demonstration of empathy, negotiation skills, nonverbal communication, sex education, etc.) of variables with some similarity (Breaking bad news, Dealing with reluctance/angry patient, explaining, giving, receiving information etc.)¹².

World over communication skills are one of the vital skills required in medical practice and considered as a core competency of undergraduate and post graduate medical education programs in developed countries¹⁴.

In our undergraduate curriculum communication skills are mainly taught in an unstructured way. After discussion of the opinions and views of the interns about the current status of communication learning and teaching it was clear to us. Whatever the students are taught, it was mainly through history taking in clinical classes in hospital ward.

In the question "how to build rapport with the patient" 89.9% answered that they should be taught about this whereas 81.2% answered that the teachers taught them. So there was disparity between expectation and happening. Aspergen et al discussed in their published article that rapport building clearly need to be taught and trained in medical school and post graduate courses¹¹.

A remarkable portion (21.6%) of interns somehow disagreed or undecided that whether they should be taught about how to explain the nature of the disease to patient and their guardians. But all interns agreed that it must be taught in a structured way either in internship or clinical settings. Many of them gave opinions that their learning must be assessed by OSCE or other through an assessment procedure which will help to retain their knowledge for a long time. This view is similar with the findings of others, who claimed that the short training course and assessment within clinical clerkship showed a long term effect².

In the question whether the interns were taught in the undergraduate classes 'how to convince the patient to do necessary investigations', most of them (72.7%) agreed that they were taught. About 11.5% were not sure that whether they need to learn it.

Regarding learning "how to explain patient about treatment plan" majority of respondents (63.7%) answered that they were taught. But one third (36.3%)

of them told that they were not taught.

In the question whether the interns were taught in the undergraduate classes 'how to motivate the undecided and hesitated patient to receive treatment', (36.2%) answered that they were not taught this in the clinical class but most of them (83.5%) answered that it should be taught.

A good number (42.2%) of interns denied that they were taught how to convince patient and their guardian for accepting a painful procedure as a treatment. But three fourth (75.7%) of them answered that they should be taught it in their student life. But there is now structured way of learning this in internship. Some teachers taught and other don't. So it must be taught in structured way in internship. Most of the interns answered (75.7%) that they were taught how to counsel the patient about diet and life style after discharge from hospital and 80.8% of them thought that it must be taught.

More than half (57.8%) of the interns admitted that they were taught how to break bad news to the patient. But vast majority of them (80.1%) thought that they should be taught it in their clinical class. Similar findings were observed by Faiz et al¹⁰. They have shown that in case of breaking bad news by trainee, difference between pre and post test was highly significant. This finding indicates that the trainees lacked in this area of skill.

More than half (58.3%) of the interns agreed that they were taught how to handle a difficult situation that can be managed but 82.1% students thought that they should learn this in student life in a structured way. Other gave opinion that it should be learnt in intern period because in this period trainee doctors get enough time to learn this from surroundings and practical field. So their learning will be long lasting and they can discuss this with different levels of teachers.

Regarding learning "how they will convince and refer the patient to another hospital for better management" majority of the interns (79.3%) answered that they were taught. Some of them gave opinion that it can be learnt during internship. Students will learn it better in internship as they fill in the form of referral; moreover they will observe the Registrar /Asst. Registrar how they convince the patient and their guardian to refer the patient to other centre.

In the questionnaire a space was kept for comment of interns. Only 32 of them gave opinions. Most common opinion was that communication skills should be taught in clinical class methodically and must be assessed in examination. Evans et al in his study confirmed that medical students given specialized consulting skills

training significantly improved the communication skills¹⁵.

Another common comment was that this study is very good for this time. If communication skills teaching is included in the curriculum this will definitely help in reducing doctor patient chaotic relation in our country. From above findings of this study it was observed that most of the variables regarding communication skills were taught in an unstructured way. But according to interns view it should be taught more and in a structured way. This finding has a similarity with the study of Cantwell & Ramirez¹⁵. They have shown in their study that 67% junior house officers felt that they need adequate communication skills about medicine.

Conclusion:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out on a sample of Intern doctors and Clinical teachers of four medical colleges. Data were collected from 218 interns by using a self administered semi-structured questionnaire. Reviewing the findings of the study, it can be concluded that communication skills must be known by doctors. Most of the interns gave answers that they were not taught majority of the communication skills mentioned in this study in their MBBS course. But in internship period they felt that those should be taught in a structured way. Most of the interns and teachers agreed that it must be included in the curriculum so that all students would have chance to learn these skills.

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Awareness on Dental Health Checkup among the Patient Attending at Selected Hospital in Dhaka City

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Abstract

This descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted among patients in selected hospitals of Dhaka city to assess awareness of dental health checkup during September to December 2011. The selection of patients was purposive and 150 patients were included in the study. The results revealed that there is a gulf of difference between the awareness and practice on oral hygiene. The mean age of the patients was 35.75±12.03 years. The study also revealed that 65.3% patients brush their teeth once daily and 52% brush only before their breakfast, 18.7% before breakfast and before going to bed. Among the patients 38% visited a dentist for more than one year for cleaning purpose, a very few (10%) visited before 6 months. Two-third majority of the patients (66%) know that consumption of sweet food can cause caries and the rest (34%) had no idea. There is statistically significant association between the age of the patients and the materials used for cleaning teeth, sex and habit of taking tobacco (P=0.000). Statistically significant association was also observed between occupation of patients and habit of taking tobacco and also between age of the patients and habit of chewing areca nut and lime (P = 0.000). So, it is necessary for everyone to have dental health checkup to look at the health of mouth, find existing problem and discuss a planned treatment with a dental surgeon. It will help to take further steps to minimize future problem of oral cavity.

Key words: Dental Caries, Awareness, Knowledge, Parents, Prevention

Introduction

Health is a universal human need for all cultural groups. General health cannot be attained or maintained without oral health. The mouth is regarded as the mirror of the body and the gateway to good health. Today, various types of oral health maintenance materials are used and countless numbers of dental health information programs are conducted in schools and other settings. However, these efforts will not succeed in influencing

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the behavior until people are not aware of the importance of oral health. So, attainment of good oral health is based upon the awareness of good dietary habits and oral hygiene practices. Individuals become aware of anything new by showing interest in knowing more about it and evaluating advantages and disadvantages to put that new idea or method in practice. Finally the individual accepts the idea as beneficial to him/her by practicing it in principle.¹⁻⁵ The people with kidney disease and those on dialysis are more likely to have periodontal disease and other oral health problems than the general population. Buildup of bacteria in the mouth can cause infection. Because people with kidney disease have weakened immune systems, they are more susceptible to infections. The inflammation caused by periodontal disease is a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Regular visits to a dentist can cut risk of infection and periodontal disease.⁷ When brushing and flossing, proper technique is the key. Immediate risks include gingivitis, cavities, tooth decay, and other gum diseases which can eventually result in oral cancer. This "silent epidemic" can be avoided by regular treatment at home and by making dental visits twice a year. While practicing good oral hygiene is vital to health, there is only one option that personal oral hygiene maintenance can do. A normal person can easily overlook conditions that could greatly complicate or even end one's life.

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Thus, visiting a dentist for regular checkup is vital to a healthier smile.⁶ A dental checkup is where a dentist, a oral health therapist or a dental therapist looks at the teeth, gums, lips, tongue and saliva to observe if they are healthy. Dental checkup is important to look at the health of the mouth, find existing problem and discuss for planned treatment. Steps to help minimize further problems can also be explained. Good oral health is important for general health and wellbeing. Better oral health can lead to better general health.⁷

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted to assess awareness of dental health checkup among the patients attending in three selected hospitals in Dhaka city. The economic status and literacy level of these patients were the selection criteria. The hospitals selected were private and semi-government run in different locations of city. The sample size was 150 patients, selected purposively. A pre-tested questionnaire consisting of questions about socio-eco-demographic characteristics of patients, knowledge about dental care and food habit, maintenance of oral hygiene and knowledge about necessity of dental care seeking prior to visiting a dental surgeon was used for collection of data. The questionnaire was administered by the investigators themselves. Data were collected by interview technique. The patients were given clear explanations about the objectives of the study and verbal informed consent was taken from them. All the data were entered into the computer and analyzed by using SPSS 16.0 software program. The Chi-square test and multiple logistic regression analyses were made to measure the extent of association.

Results

The socio-eco-demographic characteristics of patients are shown in Table 1. The maximum 39.3% patients were in the age group of 30 to 39 years and the minimum 0.7% patients were in age group of more than 70 years with 46% female and 54% male. The highest 24.7% patients' family income was between 16 to 20 thousand BDT per month and the lowest 7.3% patients' family income was more than 40 thousand BDT. About 38% patients completed higher secondary or equivalent and 32% were graduates, 6.7% were master degree holders. Likewise, 6.7% completed primary whereas 14% completed SSC or equivalent.

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Table 1: Distribution of the patients according to socio-demographic characteristics (n=300)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
10-19	7	4.7
20-29	34	22.7
30-39	59	39.3
40-49	25	16.7
50-59	17	11.3
60-69	7	4.7
≥70	1	0.7
Sex		
Male	81	54
Female	69	46
Occupation		
Housewife	52	34.7
Hindu	7	5.8
Service holder	42	28
Business	23	15.3
Education level		
Illiterate	4	2.7
Primary	10	6.7
Secondary	21	14
Higher secondary	57	38
Bachelors	48	32
Masters	10	6.7
Monthly income		
10000-15000	26	17.3
16000-20000	37	24.7
21000-25000	22	14.7
26000-30000	30	20
31000-35000	11	7.3
36000-40000	13	8.7
>40000	11	7.3

The distribution of the patients according to oral health related knowledge, oral hygiene related behavior and tobacco related habits are shown in Table 2. Here the majority of the patients brush their teeth by using tooth paste (84.7%), 9.3% by tooth powder, only 2% by herbal products. More than half (65.3%) of the patients brush their teeth once daily. Moreover, maximum 38% of them visit to dentist more than 1 years for cleaning purpose, 28.7% visit after 1 year, 23.3% visit within 6 months to 1 year and very few only 10% visit before 6 months. 43% were current smoker and 45% always chewed betel leaf.

In addition, in Table 3 there is statistically significant association between age of the patients and the material used for cleaning teeth, also between sex of patients and habit of taking tobacco (P = 0.000), between occupation of patients and habit of taking tobacco, age of patients and habit of chewing areca nut (P = 0.000). Also there is statistically significant association between frequency of cleaning teeth and monthly income of patients (P = 0.050). Another statistically significant association was observed between age of patients and whether sweet food can cause dental caries (P = 0.023) and statistically highly significant association between monthly income of patients and whether sweet food can cause dental

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caries was observed (P = 0.013).

Table 2: Distribution of the patients according to oral health related knowledge, oral hygiene related behavior, habit related factors (n=150)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Materials use for cleaning		
Tooth paste	127	84.7
Tooth powder	14	9.3
Herbal Products	3	2
Habit of chewing areca nut and lime.		
Areca nut	45	30
Tobacco	43	28.7
Frequency of cleaning teeth		
Once daily	98	65.3%
Twice Daily	52	34.7%
Visit to dentist for cleaning teeth		
Before 6 months	15	10
Within 6 months to 1 year	35	23.3
After 1 year	43	28.7
Knowledge about sweet food can cause dental caries		
Yes	99	66
No	51	34

Table 3 : Distribution of the patients according to socio-demographic characteristics and its association with oral health related knowledge, oral hygiene related behavior, habit related factors (n=150)

Variables	P - value
age of the respondent and material use for cleaning	0.000
sex of the respondent and habit of taking tobacco	0.000
frequency of cleaning teeth and monthly income	0.050
Occupation of the respondent and habit of taking tobacco	0.000
age of the respondent and habit of taking areca nut lime	0.000
Age of the respondent and knowledge about sweet food can cause dental caries.	0.023
Knowledge about sweet food can cause dental caries and monthly income	0.013

Discussion

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. We attempted to know to what extent improvements in dental health could be attributed to organized dental programs. The present study found a high percentage of patients visit the dentist after more than 1 year period and brush their teeth once in a day. It is tempting to present the data as a cause-effect relationship, whether increased resources have consequently led to an improved health situation. In a study in 2001 showed that among those aged 16-24 there has only been a 4% take regular dental check-up, with a similar level (6%) among 25-34 year olds. Furthermore, 15% of those aged between 35-44 and 24% of those aged over 45 years take up dental check up. The most marked change

in seeking dental check-up was among dentate adults aged 55-8. In the present study, most of the patients from three different hospitals were in between 30-39 years of age (39.3%), 22.7% in 20-29 years of age, 16.7% in 40-49 years of age, 11.3% in 50-59 years of age, 4.7% in 10-19 and 60-69 years of age, only a very few 0.7% in more than 70 years of age. In another study in U.K, 2008 showed that 16% visited a dentist for a check-up; 55%, more women than men, reported having a dental visit within the past 12 months.⁹ In a study in 2008 in India showed that, less than half (47.3%) of the study participants were aware of any one of the good practices for maintaining dental health, e.g., brushing teeth, periodic dental check-up, etc. 36.5% of the participants knew about practices that are bad for the teeth, such as eating too much of sweet, excess sugar, sweetened drinks.¹⁰

The present study showed that (23.3%) patients visited a dentist 6 months to 1 year for only purpose, 28.7% visited after 1 year, a very few only 10%, visited before 6 months. About 66% know that consuming of sweet food can cause caries and the rest 34% had no idea. The oral health complications reportedly associated with diabetes include tooth loss, gingivitis, periodontitis and oral soft-tissue pathologies because patients with diabetes are at an increased risk of developing oral diseases. It is generally accepted that diabetes increases the prevalence and severity of periodontitis.¹¹⁻²³ In 2010 in a study conducted in India showed that, 23.7% of the subjects were used to smoking, 3.3% subjects chewed tobacco and 8.6% subjects were used to taking alcohol.²⁴ The present study showed that, 28.7% take tobacco, 36% take spicy food and 30% take areca nut and lime. In a study in Tanzania, 2007 showed that, many people do brush their teeth at least once a day but lack the knowledge of proper tooth brushing. Tooth brushing at least once a day was reported by 92.1% of the children and 71.9% used toothpaste.²⁵ In this present study, most of the patients brush their teeth once daily (65.3%) and 34.7% twice daily. About 65% use tooth paste for cleaning teeth. In Jordan in 2002 a study was conducted which showed that 80% of the parents knew about the harmful effect of sugar and 79% thought that poor oral hygiene may induce dental caries.²⁶ The present study showed that most of the patients, 66% know that consumption of sweet food can cause caries and the rest 34% had no idea. Diabetes is one of the major cause of chronic kidney disease. If renal disease is caused by diabetes, one should know that those with diabetes are more prone to dental problems like gum disease and tooth decay. Because diabetes can affect dental health, it's important to let the dentist know that he/she is diabetic.

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27-28 Patients having known the risk factors for periodontal disease, such as smoking and diabetes, also may require more frequent maintenance visits at shorter intervals.²⁹ A study in India in 2008 showed that, of the participants, 27.9% were current tobacco users.³⁰ The present study showed that, 28.7% take tobacco among the patients.

Kidney patients are advised to tell their kidney doctor when a dental procedure is required. The doctor may recommend antibiotics be taken prior to the procedure to help guard against infection. Both gum disease and tooth decay are treatable and preventable; following the dentist's recommendations regarding brushing, flossing, exams twice a year and professional teeth cleaning can help teeth and gums stay healthy.³¹ If diabetes is not managed well, saliva may have high glucose levels. Bacteria can feed on the glucose and release more acids which can wear away at tooth enamel. Also, high levels of plaque in the mouth can lead to tartar buildup. Infections are a problem for diabetics. Diabetes slows down the healing process, and an infection from advanced tooth decay or gum disease can take a longer time to heal. Regular dental checkup and following the dentist's recommendations regarding hygiene can prevent an infection or stop one from getting worse.³² The associations and linkages between oral infections and serious systemic diseases such as diabetes have been reported thoroughly in the recent surgeon general's report, which concludes that oral health and general health are inseparable.³³

Conclusion

Good oral hygiene is important for maintaining one's overall health. The oral health complications reportedly associated with diabetes include tooth loss, gingivitis, periodontitis and oral soft-tissue pathologies. Because patients with diabetes are at an increased risk of developing oral diseases, reliable and up-to-date information regarding oral health behaviors and perceptions in diabetic populations is needed to develop effective prevention strategies that are useful for dental practitioners. Furthermore, in increasing the social acceptability concerning dental health as a part of the quality of life and in modifying social inequities in the dental services. Longitudinal studies will be necessary to evaluate the real achievements of dental programs in question by measuring their ability to secure the dental health of older adults and ultimately their general health. Both tooth decay and gum disease can be treated and are preventable if caught in its early stages. The preventable measures are like brushing twice a day, flossing once a day, visiting the dentist twice a year for checkup and playing a role model by the parents for

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children by practicing good oral health care habits.

Within the limitations of the present study, it can be recommended that provision of dental care should focus on empowering the community through information, education and communication activities. This dual strategy will aid in not just controlling oral diseases by increasing preventive care but also change attitudes so as to increase acceptability of services leading to greater utilization of curative care. Incorporating primary as well as rehabilitative dental care services, through onsite programs (at grass root level) and domiciliary visits, steps should be taken to remove the barriers to equitable access to routine care for promoting oral health of the all age specially elderly in developing countries.

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The Evaluation of Cardiac Emergency Management in National Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Abstract

Emergency department is one of the most important part of the hospital and also vulnerable to criticism. The reputation of a hospital rests to a large extent on the service of emergency department. The sudden and unexpected nature of the emergency produces panic and psychological disturbances to the relatives, which must be valued and borne in mind during organization and management of services. A descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted at Emergency Department of National Institute of Cardiovascular Hospital, Dhaka to evaluate the existing facilities, waiting time for the patients for receiving treatment, emergency referral rate and availability of health personnel, overall management and patient's suggestion to improve the services of the emergency department. A total of 150 patients were interviewed by a structured questionnaire and a checklist was utilized for equipment and drugs. The mean age of the patients was 49.59 years. 38.7% patients were attended by doctors within 6-10 minutes. Shifting of the patients from emergency department to another hospital was 12%. 87.3% patients were satisfied with time to complete treatment. In emergency department 69.3% patients were satisfied with reception facility, 89.3% patients were satisfied with given treatment, 92% patients were satisfied with doctor's service and 74% patients were satisfied with the service of the support staff. About 90% patients were satisfied with overall management. The findings of cardiac emergency services obtained through check-list were fairly comparable with the opinions expressed by the patients. For further management of emergency department patients gave suggestion for arrangement of waiting room and toilet facility, X-ray and other laboratory facility should be made available for all the duty shifts, drugs should be supplied adequately and on regular basis. They suggested for augmentation of the equipments, drugs and security and other facilities and recruitment of some trained service providers. According to the patients the Emergency Department is well-studied to manage most of the cardiac emergencies. However, specific problems identified by different stakeholders need to be critically appraised by the authority to improve the services further.

Key words: Cardiac emergency, emergency ward, emergency patient, acute, ambulance

Introduction

Emergency means serious condition that needs quick attention and immediate action. Emergency department is primarily meant for immediate medical attention and resuscitation of seriously ill patients. An Emergency Department (ED), also known as Accident & Emergency (A&E), Emergency Room (ER), Emergency Ward (EW), or Casualty Department is a medical

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treatment facility, specializing in acute care of patients who present without prior appointment, either by their own means or by ambulance.¹ The emergency departments of most hospitals operate 24 hours a day, although staffing levels may be varied in an attempt to mirror patient volume. efficient service of the emergency starts to some extent before registration of the patients and immediately after reaching the hospital. All patients attending the emergency are to be registered after a quick preliminary assessment of the severity and urgency of their ailment by the Medical Officer on duty. This is particularly an important point; clerical work involving registration, etc. should never take priority over the urgent attention to the actually ill patient.^{2,3} All particulars as per the standard format should be recorded in the emergency register. The emergency ticket should be clearly filled up for name, age, sex, date, time, emergency registration number and clinical diagnosis clearly. A summary of all the relevant clinical findings along with the medical aid given, consultations and the progress of the patient is to be noted down on emergency register (register should contain clear description of treatment details) by the attending doctor (s) before he / she is admitted or discharged or referred to secondary or tertiary hospital.¹⁰ The original emergency ticket is handed over to the patient. Emergency Department of a hospital is always blamed with mismanagement of services resulting in death or disability of a patient. Although it is not absolutely true

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in all cases as highlighted, it is conceded that some unfortunate outcomes are the result of inefficient management of emergency services. In recent years a greater understanding of the pathophysiology of ischemic heart disease and the development of promising new treatments has led to an emphasis on early intervention within the first 6 hours of ischemic onset. Animal studies suggest that this 6-hour period is the longest interval of substantial blood flow reduction before maximal and irreversible damage occurs. Like any other developing countries, Bangladesh is also experiencing an increase in the incidence of ischemic heart diseases. To reduce death and disability from cardiac diseases, the policy of the government is to provide cardiac care at an affordable cost. As a part of the endeavor, management of services to deal with cardiac emergencies is imperative.⁴⁻⁷ Prompt service-delivery should be one of the aims of Emergency Department. Over the last decade the acute heart attack / failure attending at emergency department has increased beyond the manageable capacity of many hospitals / institutes resulting in unfavorable outcomes on the fate of the patients. Patients / attendants always complain of insufficient staff and facilities at ED as the cause of delay in seeing a patient. For proper management of emergency services, doctors, nurses and health personnel should be efficient, sincere and sympathetic to the patients and equipment for transportation and resuscitation should be adequate.

The increasing demand for medical and health care services in the face of limited resources has brought to the need for careful planning and management which are considered essential if high standard of health and health care are to be achieved. Increasing the number of staff and extending the facilities may solve the problem; but it cannot be a cost-effective approach. Efficient management means maximum output at a reasonable cost.¹⁵ Ischemic heart disease and stroke are the two most common causes of death and disability in the worldwide. Over 80 percent of deaths and 85 percent of disability from Cardio-vascular Disease (CVD) occur in low- and middle-income countries. The Indian subcontinent (including India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Nepal) is home to 20 percent of the world's population and may be one of the regions with the highest burden of CVD in the world. The nature of emergency medicine (EM) has changed significantly in recent years with the advent of new technology options and the availability of more medical treatment, such as specialized intravenous thrombolysis in stroke, stent placement in acute myocardial infarction, and the use of Echocardiogram. Many of these are time-critical

procedures, leading to greater emphasis on the resuscitation, stabilization; investigation and initial management in the ED.^{8,9,14} Conditions for which patients were previously admitted and observed are now managed in the ED, allowing for direct discharge without the added cost of inpatient hospitalization. In this study, a well-known government hospital named National Institute of Cardio-vascular Disease Hospital, Dhaka was selected. Prepared questionnaire was used for collection of data from the patients or attendants attending the Emergency department. A well-through checklist also was utilized to find out the availability of the indispensable equipments and drugs at the Emergency department. The collected data was assorted and analyzed with the help of SPSS 17 software. The result was then verified and rechecked for marginal errors.

Materials Methods

The study was conducted in the period of 1st January 2012 to 30th June 2012. The study was conducted at National Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases Hospital; Dhaka, Bangladesh. The emergency room of National Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases Hospital was included in the study area. It was an observational descriptive type of study. Patients of all ages including male and female who were injured as a result of Cardiac patients attended in National Institute of Cardiovascular Disease Hospital from 24th April to 5th May 2012 were included in the study. The total number of cases during the study period was 150 which comprises of the study population (due to time limitation, within which data collected sample size fixed by convenient sampling technique). A questionnaire and a check list were designed to obtain the required information. Questionnaire was used to obtain data from the respondent. The facilities related to Cardiac patient's management at emergency department were observed and recorded with the help of the check list. Ethical issue will be considered accordingly. The researcher herself attended the National Institute of Cardiovascular Disease Hospital emergency department for collecting data. One questionnaire was used for each patient for data collection. The questionnaire was filled up the author. The interviews were concluded directly with the patients in most cases. Questions were asked in Bengali but filled in both Bengali and English form. The interview was conducted after attending to the emergency in the mentioned period. When patient was seriously ill, any other near relatives of the patient was interviewed. Both the questionnaire and checklist were

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protected and finalized. During analysis, study objectives were kept in consideration. Data processed and analyzed by using SPSS Software-17 version.

Results:

Table 1: Patient Characteristics

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	±SD
□ 20	12	8.0		
21-30	12	8.0		
31-40	26	17.3		
41-50	28	18.7	49.5	±17.522
51-60	34	22.7		
□ 61	38	25.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Table 2: Distribution of the respondent by response of whether immediately attended by any service provider

Attending by service provider	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	140	93.3
No	10	6.7
Total	150	100.0

[n= 150]

Table 3: Distribution of the respondent by mode of

Reception	Frequency	Percent
Cordially received	117	78.0
Not Cordially received	33	22.0
Total	150	100.0

reception

[n= 150]

Table 4: Distribution of the respondent by the

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satisfaction level regarding reception facility in ED of the hospital

[n= 150]

Satisfaction level	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	2	1.3
Satisfied	104	69.3
Poorly satisfied	41	27.3
Dissatisfied	3	2.0
Total	150	100.0

satisfaction level regarding reception facility in ED of the hospital

[n= 150]

Waiting time (min)	Frequency	Percent	Mean	±SD
□ 5	58	38.7		
6-10	55	36.7		
11-15	26	17.3	±6.21017	9.7487
16-20	6	4.0		
>20	5	3.3		
Total	150	100.0		

Table 6: Distribution of the respondent by opinion about doctor's service in ED of the hospital

Satisfaction level	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	8	5.3
Satisfied	138	
Poorly satisfied	4	2.7
Total	150	100.0

Table 7: Distribution of the respondent by opinion about service provided by support staff in ED of the hospital

Satisfaction level	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	1	0.7
Satisfied	111	74.0
Poorly satisfied	37	24.7
Dissatisfied	1	0.7
Total	150	100.0

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Table 8: Distribution of the respondent by advised urgent investigation in ED of the hospital

[n=150]

Investigation	Frequency	Percent
Yes	145	96.7
No	5	3.3
Total	150	100.0

Table 9: Distribution of the respondent according to their perceived clear diagnosis of disease in ED of the hospital

[n=150]

Disease Diagnosis	Frequency	Percent
Diagnosed	140	93.3
Not diagnosed	10	6.7
Total	150	100.0

Table 10: Distribution of the respondent by their satisfaction upon treatment given in ED of the hospital

[n=150]

Satisfaction level	Frequency	Percent
Highly satisfied	3	2.0
Satisfied	134	89.3
Poorly satisfied	13	8.7
Total	150	100.0

Table 11: Distribution of the respondent by type of treatment given to them

[n=150]

Treatment	Frequency	Percent
First aid	40	26.7
Observation	22	14.7
Admission	70	46.7
Referred to another hospital	18	12.0
Total	150	100.0

reception

[n= 150]

Table 4: Distribution of the respondent by the

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Table 12: Distribution of the respondent by time required to complete treatment in ED of the hospital

[n=150]

Time (min)	Frequency	Percent	Mean	SD
□ 10	20	13.3		
11-15	36	24.0		
16-30	60	40.0		
31-45	15	10.0	29.2467	±24.3800
46-60	6	4.0		
>60	13	8.7		
Total	150	100.0		

Table 13: Drugs available in ED (according to the Standard Operation Procedure of District Hospital)

Name of the Drugs	Present / Absent
Spray Nitroglycerine	Present
Tablet Nitroglycerine	Present
Injection Pathedine	Present
Injection Morphine	Present
Injection Streptokinase	Absent
Injection Adrenalin	Present
Injection Dopamin	Present
Injection Frusemide	Present
Tablet Frusemide	Present
Injection Hydrocortisone	Present
Tablet -blocker	Present
Tablet Ca-channel blocker	Present
Tablet ACE inhibitor	Present
Tablet Amlodipine	Present
Tablet Ranitidine	Present
Injection Ranitidine	Present
Antiseptic Liquid	Present
Injection Diazepam	Present
Injection Ketorolac	Present
Antiseptic liquid	Absent

Table 5: Distribution of the respondent by waiting time to attend by a doctor (service provider) in ED of the hospital

[n=150]

Discussion:

A descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted at Emergency Department of National Institute of Cardiovascular Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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emergency services in tertiary level hospitals of Bangladesh.

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reported that due to urgent investigation done in the hospital, the disease was diagnosed promptly. 69.3 % of the patients were satisfied regarding reception facility at ED as they were received by service provider immediately. On the other hand, 74 % patients were satisfied about services provided by support staff. Regarding doctors service this study shows that the service was very good. Most of the patients, 92% were satisfied about doctors service, 89.3 % patients were satisfied with the treatment they received from the ED. Furthermore, 95.3 % patients were satisfied with the cleanliness of ED, 87.3 % patients were satisfied with the time required to complete treatment. About overall management of ED, 90 % patients were satisfied. These findings are more or less analogous to those of Aziz et al. There were a total of 22 service providers. Among them, 45.5% were doctors, 18.2 % were support staff, 9.10% were cleaners and 4.6% were paramedics and gatemen who provide services round the clock by shifting duties. The ED is well equipped. Most of the facilities are present in ED except waiting room, toilet facility and availability of adequate number of bed. The other diagnostic facilities like X-ray, Echocardiogram, CT- Angiogram, Blood for Troponin-I, CBC, Lipid Profile, Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine are not available specially in ED but those are available in the hospital. Drug supply was also inadequate as per demand of the patients. Most of the instrument are available in ED except Ausculto, Tape measure, Height scale, Suturing material, Sterilizer, Stomach tube and Autoclave machine. According to the Standard Operation Procedure (SOP), 20 emergency drugs were listed. Out of them Injection Streptokinase, Antiseptic liquid were not available.

Conclusion

From the study it was found that emergency department was more or less clean but not well equipped and well staffed. More posts should be created for trained Emergency Medical Officers for management of emergency case. There is no waiting room for emergency department. So attendants and visitors move around aimlessly and create problem in management of emergency patient. There is no toilet facility for the patient in ED which is extremely needed. Proper diagnosis is an essential part for management of treatment. Diagnostic facilities for emergency patients of ED in this hospital are available to some extent like ECG but other diagnostic facilities like X-ray and Echocardiogram, should be available round the clock. Drugs are the vital part of treatment which are not available in ED as per need of the patients. The findings of this study will be helpful in the improvement of the

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The Ozone: Protecting the Oral Environ.....

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Abstract

Oxygen/ozone therapy is a term that describes a number of different practices in which oxygen, ozone, or hydrogen peroxide are administered via gas or water to kill disease microorganisms, improve cellular function, and promote the healing of damaged tissues. Ozone gas is immunostimulating, potent analgesic, detoxifying, antimicrobial, bioenergetic and biosynthetic properties as it causes activation of the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins and lipids. The use of ozone has been advocated in Medical and Dental science due to its excellent antimicrobial, disinfectant and effervescent properties. The purpose of this article is to review the therapeutic applications of ozonated products in dentistry.

Introduction

The word ozone is derived from the Greek word ozein (odorant).¹ Ozone (O₃) is a triatomic molecule, consisting of three oxygen atoms. Its molecular weight is 47.98 g/mol. Ozone is thermodynamically highly unstable compound that, dependent on system conditions like temperature and pressure, decomposes to pure oxygen with a short half-life.² The German chemist, Schonbein, first discovered ozone in 1840. The first medical application was in 1870 when Lender purified blood in test tubes with ozone.³ In the 1920's Edwin , a Swiss dentist started to use O₃ as part of his disinfection system.¹ As of 1929, more than 114 diseases were listed for treatment with oxygen/ozone therapy.³

Ozone is one of the most powerful antimicrobial agents available for use in medicine and dentistry.¹ Early in its history ozone was found to oxidize a spectrum of organic compounds and to interact with unsaturated chemical bonds.⁴ Since ozone is a powerful oxidizer, it effectively kills bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites at a dramatically lower concentration than chlorine, with

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none of the toxic side effects. One molecule of ozone is equal to about 3,000 to 10,000 molecules of chlorine and it kills pathogenic organisms 3,500 times faster. Introduction of oxygen/ozone therapy has truly revolutionized dentistry. This newer concept addresses the multifactorial infective states within the oral cavity in an effective, safe, nontoxic manner.³

In dental practice ozone therapy was first evaluated in 1933 for the treatment of oral lesions and chronic periodontal infections. Intraoral, ozone can be used to treat chronic periodontitis, caries, infections after dental extractions, lesions caused by radiotherapy, aphthae and mycoses, and can be used for disinfecting root canals.⁵ Oxygen/ozone therapy in dentistry contains a multiplicity of protocols to deal with dental infection. Three basic forms of application to oral tissue are applied - 1) ozonated water, 2) ozonated olive oil, and 3) oxygen/ozone gas. Ozonated water and olive oil have the capacity to entrap and then release oxygen/ozone, an ideal delivery system. These forms of application are used singly or in combination to treat dental disease.⁶

Medical Ozone is made when medical grade oxygen is electrically activated (using an Ozone Generator) to form ozone. It is a mixture of the purest oxygen and purest ozone.⁷ In a medical/dental ozone generator, the medical grade O₂ is converted to O₃, in special tubes via a corona discharge reaction (similar to lightning). This type of generator is able to control the concentration of ozone, critical to delivering the correct doses in micrograms/milliliters (mcg/ml). Concentration is determined by exposure and contact time of the medical-grade oxygen to the 5 to 13 millivolts [Bocci] sealed-corona discharge tubes. Because of ozone's physical properties in the dental model, the ratio of ozone to oxygen is extremely low. The typical average concentration of ozone used in treatments is 25 micrograms of ozone per milliliter of oxygen/ozone gas mixture. That translates into 0.25 parts of ozone to

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99.75 parts of oxygen.³ There are three systems for generating ozone gas. Ultraviolet system produces low concentrations of ozone, used in aesthetics and for air purification. Cold plasma system is used in air and water purification. Corona discharge system produces high concentrations of ozone. It is the most common system used in the medical/ dental field. It is easy to handle and it has a controlled ozone production rate.^{3,7}

Mechanism of action

The mechanism of action for ozone therapy remains hypothetical but possible explanations of its effect is characterized by the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) during the ozonation process which function as physiological enhancers of various biological processes.⁸ It acts on cells by damaging its cytoplasmic membrane due to ozonolysis of dual bonds and also ozone-induced modification of intracellular contents (oxidation of proteins loss of organelle function) because of secondary oxidant effects. This action is non-specific and selective to microbial cells; it does not damage human body cells because of their major antioxidative ability.⁷ In viral infections the mechanism of ozone action lies in the intolerance of infected cells to peroxides and change of activity of reverse transcriptase, which takes part in synthesis of viral proteins.² Ozone influences cellular and humoral immune system; it stimulates proliferation of immunocompetent cells and synthesis of immunoglobulins. It also activates function of macrophages and increases sensitivity of microorganisms to phagocytosis.² When administered at low concentrations, the organisms own resistance is mobilized, i.e. ozone (re)activates the immune system. As a response to this activation through ozone, the body's immune cells produce special messengers called cytokines. These molecules in turn activate other immune cells, setting off a cascade of positive change throughout the immune system, which is stimulated to resist diseases.⁷ Ozone causes the synthesis of biologically active substances such as interleukins, leukotrienes and prostaglandins which is beneficial in reducing inflammation and wound healing.⁷ Ozone brings about the rise of Po₂ in tissues and improves transportation of oxygen in blood, which results in change of cellular metabolism - activation of aerobic processes (glycolysis, Krebs cycle, ?-oxidation of fatty acids) and use of energetic resources. It also prevents formation of erythrocytes, aggregates and increases their contact surface for oxygen transportation. Its ability to stimulate the circulation is used in the treatment of circulatory disorders.⁷ It also activates

mechanisms of protein synthesis, increase amount of ribosomes and mitochondria in cells. These changes on the cellular level explain elevation of functional activity and regeneration potential of tissues and organs.²

Mode of ozone administration

Direct intra-arterial and/or intravenous injection was first used by Lacoste in 1951 for circulatory compromise and possible sequelae such as gangrene. An oxygen-ozone mixture is slowly injected into an artery or vein with a hypodermic syringe. This method is used primarily for arterial circulatory disorder.^{4,8} Rectal insufflations have been used in various health problems such as ulcerative colitis, cancer, HIV-related problems and others. A mixture of ozone and oxygen is introduced through the rectum and absorbed into the body through the intestine. Intramuscular injection is commonly used to treat allergies and inflammatory diseases. Major and minor autohemotherapy involve removing an amount (usually 10 mls for minor and 50 mls for major) of the patient's blood from a vein with a hypodermic syringe. The blood is then mixed with oxygen-ozone and return to the patient intravenously. These methods have been used to treat arthritis, cancer, heart disease and HIV infection. ⁸ Ozonated water finds applications in dental surgery where it is reported to promote hemostasis, enhance local oxygen supply and inhibit bacterial proliferation. Applied following tooth extraction or during dental surgery it may also be rinsed in conditions such as thrush and periodontal disease, and swallowed to soothe gastritis. The ozone gas is bubbled through water and the water is used externally.^{4,8} Intra-articular injection is used primarily to treat arthritis, rheumatism and other joint diseases. In this method, ozone gas is bubbled through water and the mixture is injected directly between the joints. Ozone bagging is a non-invasive method that uses a specially made plastic bag that is placed around the area to be treated. An oxygen-ozone mixture is pumped into the bag and mixture is absorbed into the body through skin. Ozone bagging is primarily recommended for treating leg ulcers, gangrene, fungal infections, burns and slow healing wounds.⁸ Ozonated oils are pure plant extracts through which pure oxygen and ozone are passed. Used primarily to treat skin problems, ozone gas is added to olive oil and applied as a balm or salve for long-term, low-dose exposure.^{1,8}

Why the ozone therapy ??

Eliminates the use of drills and fillings, eliminates the use of anaesthetics, kills 99% of bacteria in cavities, can whiten discoloured cavities, excellent for nervous

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or anxious patients, reduces inflammation and pain sensation.⁷

Indications

Prophylaxis and prevention of dental caries, remineralisation of pit and fissure, root and smooth surface caries, restoration of open cavitations along with conventional conservative measures, bleaching of discoloured root canal treated teeth, endodontic treatment, desensitization of extremely sensitive tooth necks, soft tissue pathoses, treatment of infected, badly healing wounds and inflammatory process, implantology.

Contraindications and toxicity

Pregnancy, severe anaemia, hyperthyroidism, thrombocytopenia, severe myasthenia, acute alcohol intoxication, recent myocardial infarction, hemorrhage from any organ, Glucose-6-phosphatedehydrogenase deficiency and ozone allergy.^{3,9} Ozone transformation may be poisonous to pulmonary complement as good as pick organs. Complications caused by ozone caring have been sparse during 0.0007 per application. Known side effects are epiphora, upper respiratory tract irritation, rhinitis, cough, headache occasional nausea, vomiting, crispiness of breath, blood vessel swelling, bad circulation.^{3,1}

A novel therapeutic approach in dentistry:

Oral medicine

The ozone has been reported to accelerate the healing of soft tissue conditions like apthous ulcers, herpes labialis, ANUG and other gum infections.³ All viruses are susceptible to ozone's neutralizing action. Relative susceptibility in ascending order was found to be: poliovirus type 2, echovirus type 1, poliovirus type 1, coxsackie virus type B5, echovirus type 5, and coxsackie virus type A9. In pure water, at maximal solubility of ozone and room temperature, echovirus type 29 is inactivated in one minute, poliovirus type 1 in two, type 3 in three, and type 2 in seven minutes. Analysis of viral components showed damage to polypeptide chains and envelope proteins, which could result in attachment capability compromise, and breakage of the single-stranded RNA producing replicating dysfunction. Lipid-enveloped viruses are sensitive to treatment with ether, organic solvents, and ozone, indicating that disruption or loss of lipids results in impaired or destroyed infectivity. Viruses containing lipid envelopes include the Hepadnaviridae (Hepatitis B), the Flaviviridae (hepatitis C, West Nile virus, yellow fever); the Herpesviridae, a large family

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grouping the Simplex, Varicella-Zoster, Cytomegalovirus, and Epstein-Barr viruses; the Orthomyxoviridae (avian influenza); the Paramyxoviridae (mumps, measles); the Coronaviridae (SARS); the Rhabdoviridae (rabies); the Togaviridae (Rubella, encephalitis); the Bunyaviridae (Hantavirus); the Poxviridae (smallpox); and the Retroviridae (HIV), among others. Indeed, once the virion's lipid envelope becomes fragmented, its DNA or RNA core cannot survive. ²

Prosthetic

Denture plaque control is essential for the prevention of denture stomatitis. Arita et al. assessed the effect of ozonated water and found no viable *C. albicans* following exposure to flowing ozonated water (2 or 4 mg/l) for one minute.⁷ Direct exposure to gaseous ozone was a more effective microbicide compared with ozonated water.⁹

Oral surgery

In chronic mandibular osteomyelitis, it was observed that medical ozone exposure promoted more complete and rapid normalization of nonspecific resistance and T-cellular immunity, thus accelerating clinical cure and reducing the incidence of complications. Dental extraction becomes possible in a patient with avascular bisphosphonate-related jaw osteonecrosis or in those who received pyrophosphate analogues when treated with ozone therapy.⁹ Ozone encourages wound healing as well as controls opportunistic infections, daily treatment with ozonated water accelerates the physiological healing.¹ Application of ozone therapy after tooth extraction and in case of post-extraction complications, was found quite useful.⁷

Periodontics

Periodontal disease is a multifactorial disease process in the mouth.¹⁰ Due to the physics of a gas entering into a liquid, the crevicular fluids and the epithelial tissues lining the sulcus absorb the oxygen/ozone mixture, ensuring complete anaerobic pathogen load elimination. In addition the tissue responds with increased perfusion and immunological activity allowing for enhanced healing.³ Ozonated water has strong bactericidal activity against bacteria in plaque biofilm. Ozonated water (0.5 to 4 mg/l) was found to be highly effective in killing both gram - positive and gram - negative microorganisms. Gram - negative bacteria such as *Porphyrromonas gingivalis*, *Porphyrromonas endodontalis* were more sensitive to ozonated water than gram positive oral streptococci and *Candida albicans* in pure culture.¹ Application of ozone,

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desensitization of dentine lasts for longer period of time. Smear layer present over the exposed root surface prevents the penetration of calcium and fluoride ions deep into the dentinal tubules. Ozone removes this smear layer, opens up the dentinal tubules, broadens their diameter and allows the Calcium and Fluoride ions to flow into the tubules easily, deeply and effectively to plug the dentinal tubules.⁹

Operative dentistry

Oxygen/ozone can be utilized for pit and fissure sealants, caries removal, cavity preparation, crown & bridge preparation and reduce carious exposure.³ The procedure is to isolate the tooth or preparation and flow the gas into the area, the area to be treated slowly for 45-60 seconds. The use of proper evacuation technique is essential to avoid inhalation of gas. This procedure will kill or significantly inhibit any possible microbial infection at the site with a reduction of postoperative hypersensitivity.¹⁰ In cases of incipient caries, ozone can kill bacteria in the demineralized part and demineralized tooth structure then, can be mineralized using a special remineralized kit containing calcium, fluoride, phosphorus and sodium, all in their ionic form.³ Since oxygen is the only gas that can carry an electrical charge, this opposite charge phenomena attracts ozone to the area and the pathogens are killed. Taking into consideration the routes of oxygen/ozone application, root canal therapy goes through a paradigm change. The additions to treatment are as follows: Files are coated with ozonated olive oil for lubrication and disinfection. The canals are prepared, irrigated with ozonated water, and dried. The final step before filling each canal is slow insufflation with oxygen/ozone gas. The insufflation process allows the molecular oxygen/ozone to travel into the canals, lateral canals, and tubules. The molecular oxygen/ozone can travel through the tubules and kill the positively charged microbes and perform a true sterilization. The results following the use of above steps have shown less post operative complications, fewer retreatments and no reinfection of dentition.^{3,6}

Conclusion

In comparison with classical medicine modalities such as antibiotics and disinfectants, ozone therapy is quite inexpensive, atraumatic, biologically based treatment and is used in almost all aspects of dentistry. Ozone is the perfect substance for use in dental procedures. It disinfects the tissues treated and leaves no toxic residues like chlorinated products. It performs this task by oxidizing the cell membranes of pathogenic organisms and killing them. Used as a preventive agent in pit and fissure caries and as a therapeutic agent in

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primary root caries. Used as an irrigating agent in endodontic, and adjuvant in periodontal surgical and maintenance phase. Ozone therapy shows considerable promise and dentists should be aware of these developments and follow its progress. Though the evidence for this novel preventive treatment option is currently insufficient to make widespread recommendations, changes in dental practice should be explored to see how oral health can be best supported through novel preventive systems.

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Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome- A Life Threatening Sleep Disorder: Proper Diagnosis and Treatment is Essential

M M Hasan¹, M Zaki²

Abstract

Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome is a life threatening sleep disorder which can occur as consequences of some body conditions. On the other hand it causes many systemic diseases as well as accidental injury. There is no prevalence study in Bangladesh but its prevalence is higher in western countries. Proper diagnosis and treatment is essential. Surgical treatment of this disease gives permanent cure. Maxillofacial surgeon has a vital role in treating this disease. ENT surgeon as well as prosthodontist can help the OSAS patient as well.

Key words: OSAS- Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome, AHI-Apnea- hypopnea Index, REM- Rapid Eye Movement, EEG- Electro Encephalogram, EMG- Electro myoeogram, EOG- Electro Oculogram, CPAP- Continuous Positive Airway pressure, MRA- Mandibular Repositioning Appliance, MMA- Maxillo Mandibular Advancement

Obstructive sleep apnea is a breathing disorder which is caused by the obstruction of upper airway. It is characterized by repetitive pauses in breathing during sleep. This pause in the breath is called apnea which typically lasts for 20-40 seconds, resulting in reduction in blood oxygen saturation. It is believed that 1 in 5 American adults (20%) have mild OSA¹. In 2006, a population-based survey in north India had estimated the prevalence of OSAS at 3.6 per cent (males and females being 4.9 and 2.1% respectively)². In Bangladesh no such study was carried out.

Most cases of OSAS are caused by i) structural features which give rise to narrowed airway, ii) increased soft tissue around the airway, iii) decreased muscle tone, iv) old age and v) brain injury.

The pathophysiology of OSAS is such that during Rapid Eye Movement (REM), sleep in particular, muscle tone of the throat and neck, as well as the vast majority of all skeletal muscles are almost completely attenuated, allowing the tongue and soft palate/oropharynx to relax and in the case of sleep apnea, to impede the flow of air to a degree ranging from light snoring to complete collapse. In the cases where airflow is reduced to a degree where blood oxygen level falls or the physical exertion to breathe is great, neurological mechanism triggers and a sudden interruption of sleep occurs which is called a neurological arousal. These arousals rarely result in complete awakening but have a

significant negative effect on the restorative quality of sleep. Severity of OSA can be measured by Apnea-hypopnea index. The apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) is an index of sleep apnea severity that combines apneas and hypopneas. The apneas (pauses in breathing) must last for at least 10 seconds and are associated with a decrease in blood oxygenation. Combining these give an overall sleep apnea severity score that evaluates both number of sleep disruptions and degree of oxygen desaturation (low blood level). The AHI is calculated by dividing the number of events by the number of hours of sleep. (AHI values are typically categorized as 5-15/hr = mild; 15-30/hr = moderate; and > 30/h = severe.)³

During apneic episodes, arterial blood oxygen saturation decreases, and sympathetic activity and blood pressure increases. Each apneic episode is ended with an arousal from sleep, resulting in marked fragmentation of sleep in affected individuals. Excessive daytime sleepiness is a major consequence of OSA. OSA has also been linked to significant conditions such as hypertension^{4,5,6}, ischaemic heart disease and stroke⁷, premature death⁸, and impairment of cognitive functions⁹ which may contribute to motor vehicle and workplace related accidents (comparable to functioning while intoxicated)^{10,11}. A study of The University of British Columbia demonstrated that a person with OSA is twice as likely to be involved in a motor vehicle accident¹². For untreated individuals, it has been established that there is a 37% higher 5-year morbidity and mortality rate¹³. Moreover, it was also estimated in 2008 that the average additional annual health care cost of an untreated sleep apnea patient is US \$1,336 contributing an estimated total of \$3.4 billion/year additional medical costs in the U.S.¹⁴. In Australia, the financial burden of OSA (including healthcare costs, lost productivity, road accidents and work-related accidents) is in the range of AU \$2-8 billion per year¹⁵.

Diagnosis of OSAS is based on a combination of patient

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history and lab test specially polysomnography, which is the gold standard for the diagnosis of OSAS. Polysomnography is a multiparameter test which monitors brain (EEG), muscle activity or skeletal muscle activation(EMG), eye movements (EOG), and heart rhythm (ECG) during sleep. But this procedure is inconvenient to the patient as well as it requires sophisticated specialist facilities, technical and scientific staff and sleep clinicians.

Although PSG helps identify individuals who have OSA and help the management, it does not identify the site of obstruction or predict surgical outcome. Polysomnography has been used in children for more than 30 years and is accepted as the most comprehensive and accurate method of determining the presence and severity of OSA in children. However, it is expensive, time- and labor-consuming, intrusive, and not readily available to children in many communities. Alternative or abbreviated testing is desirable.¹⁶ Diagnosis of OSA with polysomnography is more cost effective and not readily available in all centres.¹⁷ More over that polysomnographic studies are usually performed in a dedicated sleep laboratory with supervision by a sleep technician and the resulting data require time-consuming analysis. Thus, many attempts have been made to simplify the diagnostic process for patients suspected of having sleep-related breathing disorders.¹⁸

Imaging has also adjunctive role in the diagnosis and treatment planning of OSAS, among which cephalometry is one. But cephalometry due to its two dimensional representation are lacking of information about the airway volume and dimensions.¹⁹ Also due to the difference in the posture during cephalometry sleep may create an underestimation.

Both CT Scans and MRIs are beginning to play a crucial role in the evaluation of patients before surgical treatment (Maxillo Mandibular Advancement, Uvulopalatopharyngoplasty, reduction of tongue base or genioid muscle surgery) as well as non surgical treatment..

The treatment of OSA is determined by patients medical history, the severity of the disorders and most importantly, the specific cause of the obstruction. Mild apnea can be treated by behavioral therapy, moderate or severe OSA requires more significant interventions. Nasal Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP) or Mandibular Repositioning Appliance (MRA). But neither CPAP nor MRA are cures for OSA. For these patients advancement surgery of both the maxilla and mandible (Maxillo Mandibular Advancement surgery-

MMA) is performed to eliminate or improve symptoms of the condition by increasing the size of the airway. MMA resulted in an 83% reduction in the group mean apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) when diagnosis and planning was based on cephalometric analysis²⁰. This treatment option is based on a permanent alteration of the maxillary and mandibular anatomy including the attached soft tissue. Study of Conley showed that the MMA surgical option is more successful than MRA.²¹ Maxillofacial surgeon plays the key role in MMA surgery which is a type of orthognathic surgery.

Conclusion:

Treatment reduces the health consequences of OSA. Imaging is valuable in determining sites of potential airway obstruction to direct treatment of the specific causes of obstruction to improve CPAP tolerance and assist in dental and nasal treatment planning. Maxillofacial surgeon as well as the ENT surgeon can combinedly work together to solve the problem. Sleep apnea diagnosis and treatment is essential to fight to turn the deadly "Choke and Gasp" cycle into a good night's sleep for patients and their loved ones.

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Pulpal Diagnosis of Primary Teeth: Guidelines for Clinical Practice

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Abstract

Diagnosis of pulp status is an important clinical step to achieve success in pulp therapy technique or endodontic treatment in children. In pediatric dentistry, history of symptoms given by a child may not be reliable. Assessment of dental pulp status plays an important role. It is hoped that these guidelines will facilitate pulpal diagnosis, good decision-making and evidence-based practice for pediatric patients.

Key words: pulpal diagnosis, guidelines, primary teeth

Introduction

Accurate diagnosis of the pulp status is an important step to achieve success in endodontic therapy. Frequently, this is overlooked in pediatric patients by clinicians. This can result in incorrect treatment plan. The diagnosis should be based on present clinical symptoms, history of symptoms, diagnostic tests and clinical findings. Various tests have been used for a variety of different pulpal diagnostic terms in the past¹. While doing this procedure, we should remember that responses given by patients are subjective as some children may exaggerate the symptoms due to fear and anxiety². The indications, objectives, and type of pulpal therapy depend on whether the pulp is vital or non-vital, based on the clinical diagnosis of normal pulp (symptom free and normally responsive to vitality testing), reversible pulpitis (pulp capable of healing), symptomatic or asymptomatic irreversible pulpitis (vital inflamed pulp is incapable of healing), or necrotic pulp³.

Clinical classification of pulpal conditions

According to diagnostic chart⁴ of the department of Periodontics and Endodontics, University at Buffalo, pulpal conditions may be of five types:

1. Normal Pulp

A pulpal condition, usually called normal, in which the pulp responds to thermal and electrical tests in a manner similar to that of a corresponding control tooth.

2. Hypersensitive Dentin

A pulpal condition, with no apparent histologic

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changes, in which the patient feels pain when the dentin is exposed to touch from a dental explorer, fingernail or tooth brush and to thermal or to other stimuli. However, the pain disappears when the stimulus is removed.

3. Reversible Pulpitis

(Syn: hyperemia, inflamed-reversibly)

A pulpal condition is commonly induced by dental caries and operative procedures, in which the patient responds to thermal or osmotic stimuli, but the symptoms disappear when the etiology is eliminated.

4. Irreversible Pulpitis

a) Irreversible pulpitis without periapical pathosis

A pulpal condition, usually caused by deep dental caries or restorations, in which spontaneous pain may occur or be precipitated by thermal or other stimuli. Radiographs show no periapical changes. The pain lasts for several minutes to hours.

b) Irreversible pulpitis with periapical pathosis

A pulpal condition similar to above, but in which periapical or lateral radiographic changes are evident.

5. Necrotic Pulp

a) Necrotic pulp without periapical pathosis

A pulpal condition in which there may or may not be spontaneous, moderate to severe pain or pain elicited by various stimuli. Response to various testing modalities is usually absent. Radiographic changes are not evident.

b) Necrotic pulp with periapical pathosis

A pulpal condition similar to above, except that in this category periapical or lateral lesions are evident in radiographs.

Pulp Management Options:

Pulpal pathology or conditions of primary teeth can be managed either by extraction or by following treatment options as:-

" Direct pulp capping (only for non-carious exposures

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to maintain coronal and radicular pulp vitality)
" Pulpotomy (removal of coronal pulp tissue with maintenance of vitality of radicular pulp) and
" Pulpectomy (removal of coronal and radicular pulp and root canal filling)

Outline for diagnosis of pulpal status:

An outline⁵ for determining the pulpal status of curiously involved teeth in children involves the following:

1. Visual and tactile examination of carious dentin and associated periodontium
2. Radiographic examination of
 - a. periradicular and furcation areas
 - b. pulp canals
 - c. periodontal space
 - d. developing succedaneous teeth
3. History of spontaneous unprovoked pain
4. Pain from percussion
5. Pain from mastication
6. Degree of mobility
7. Palpation of surrounding soft tissues
8. Size, appearance, and amount of hemorrhage associated with pulp exposures

From the diagnostic factors, the pulpal condition of deciduous tooth may be diagnosed as in Table 1.

Guidelines for diagnosis:

Table 1: Diagnostic factors related to pulpal status

Diagnostic factors	Pulpal Status		
	Reversible Pulpitis	Irreversible Pulpitis	Pulpal Necrosis
Increased mobility	No	Yes	Yes
Tenderness on percussion	No	Yes	Often
Sensitivity	Yes	Yes	Unlikely
Radiographic or pathologic changes (thickened periodontal ligament space, or radicular disease)	No	Often	Yes
Excessive bleeding at the pulp stumps	No	Often	No
Toothache	Sometimes upon stimulation	Yes	Often
Sinus	No	No	Possible
Swelling	No	Possible	Possible

The examination should begin with a thorough history and characteristics of any pain, because these are often important in helping to determine pulpal status and eventual treatment whereas pain usually accompanies pulpal inflammation, extensive problems might arise without any history of pain. If possible, a distinction between provoked and spontaneous pain should be ascertained. Provoked pain that ceases after removal of the causative stimulation is usually reversible and indicative of minor inflammatory changes. Stimuli

include thermal, chemical, and mechanical irritants and many times are due to deep caries, faulty restorations, soreness around a primary tooth nearing exfoliation, or an erupting permanent tooth. Spontaneous pain is a constant or throbbing pain that occurs without stimulation or continues long after the causative factor has been removed. In a well-controlled histologic study of primary teeth with deep carious lesions, Guthrie et al. 1965,⁶ demonstrated that a history of spontaneous toothache is usually associated with extensive degenerative changes extending into the root canals. Primary teeth with a history of spontaneous pain should not receive vital pulp treatments and are candidates for pulpectomy or extraction.

The clinical examination might produce evidence of pulpal pathosis. Redness, swelling, fluctuance, severe dental decay, defective or missing restorations, and draining parulis might indicate pulpal involvement (Fig. 1).

Percussion sensitivity might be valuable to the diagnosis, but it is complicated by the reliability of the child's response because of the psychological aspects involved. Tooth mobility might be present normally because of physiologic resorption, and many pulpally involved teeth have no mobility.

Electric pulp tests are not valid in primary teeth.⁷ Laser Doppler flowmetry might be of greater help in determining vitality, but this equipment has not been perfected, and the price is prohibitive.⁸ Thermal tests are usually not conducted on primary teeth because of their reliability.⁷

After the clinical examination, radiographs of good quality are essential. Like permanent teeth, periapical radiolucencies appear at the apices in primary anterior teeth. In primary molars, pathologic changes most often apparent in the bifurcation or trifurcation areas. Consequently, bite-wing radiographs are often best to observe pathologic changes in posterior primary teeth. Pathologic bone and root resorptions are signs of advanced pulpal pathosis that has spread into the periapical tissues and is usually treatable only with extraction.

Internal resorption (Fig. 2) in primary teeth is always associated with extensive inflammation.⁶ Because of the thinness of primary molar roots, if internal resorption can be seen radiographically, a perforation usually exists, and the tooth must be extracted. Interpretation of radiographs of primary teeth is always complicated by the presence of the succedaneous tooth and surrounding follicle. Misinterpretation of the follicle can easily lead

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to an erroneous diagnosis of periapical pathology. Superimposition of the permanent tooth might obscure visibility of the furca and roots of the primary tooth, causing misdiagnosis.

Pulpal exposure may be clinical (Fig. 3) or radiographical (Fig. 4). The size of a pulpal exposure and the amount and color of hemorrhage have been reported as important factors in diagnosing the extent of inflammation under a carious lesion. Although all carious exposures are accompanied by pulpal inflammation, the larger the exposure, the more likely it is to be widespread or necrotic. Excessive^{9,10} or deep purple colored¹⁰ hemorrhage is evidence of extensive inflammation, and these teeth are candidates for pulpectomy or extraction. Hemorrhage that cannot be controlled within 1-2 minutes by light pressure with a damp cotton pellet at an exposure site indicates more extensive treatment. The same is true after removal of tissue when doing a pulpotomy. A pulpectomy or extraction is then indicated.

The guidelines for diagnosis and treatment plan for primary teeth are summarized in Table 2.

Conclusion:

Diagnosis of pulpal condition is very much important in

Fig. 1: Redness and fluctuant swelling

Fig. 2: Internal resorption

Fig. 3: Clinically exposed pulp

Fig. 4: Radiographic pulp exposure

the determination of most appropriate treatment for primary tooth. For proper pulpal diagnosis, thorough history, clinical and radiographic examinations should be done. These guidelines may facilitate pulpal diagnosis and good decision-making in clinical practice.

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to an erroneous diagnosis of periapical pathology. Superimposition of the permanent tooth might obscure visibility of the furca and roots of the primary tooth, causing misdiagnosis.

Pulpal exposure may be clinical (Fig. 3) or radiographical (Fig. 4). The size of a pulpal exposure and the amount and color of hemorrhage have been reported as important factors in diagnosing the extent of inflammation under a carious lesion. Although all carious exposures are accompanied by pulpal inflammation, the larger the exposure, the more likely it is to be widespread or necrotic. Excessive^{9,10} or deep purple colored¹⁰ hemorrhage is evidence of extensive inflammation, and these teeth are candidates for pulpectomy or extraction. Hemorrhage that cannot be controlled within 1-2 minutes by light pressure with a damp cotton pellet at an exposure site indicates more extensive treatment. The same is true after removal of tissue when doing a pulpotomy. A pulpectomy or extraction is then indicated.

The guidelines for diagnosis and treatment plan for primary teeth are summarized in Table 2.

Conclusion:

Diagnosis of pulpal condition is very much important in

Fig. 1: Redness and fluctuant swelling

Fig. 2: Internal resorption

Fig. 3: Clinically exposed pulp

Fig. 4: Radiographic pulp exposure

the determination of most appropriate treatment for primary tooth. For proper pulpal diagnosis, thorough history, clinical and radiographic examinations should be done. These guidelines may facilitate pulpal diagnosis and good decision-making in clinical practice.

include thermal, chemical, and mechanical irritants and many times are due to deep caries, faulty restorations, soreness around a primary tooth nearing exfoliation, or an erupting permanent tooth. Spontaneous pain is a constant or throbbing pain that occurs without stimulation or continues long after the causative factor has been removed. In a well-controlled histologic study of primary teeth with deep carious lesions, Guthrie et al. 1965,⁶ demonstrated that a history of spontaneous toothache is usually associated with extensive degenerative changes extending into the root canals. Primary teeth with a history of spontaneous pain should not receive vital pulp treatments and are candidates for pulpectomy or extraction.

The clinical examination might produce evidence of pulpal pathosis. Redness, swelling, fluctuance, severe dental decay, defective or missing restorations, and draining parulis might indicate pulpal involvement (Fig. 1).

Percussion sensitivity might be valuable to the diagnosis, but it is complicated by the reliability of the child's response because of the psychological aspects involved. Tooth mobility might be present normally because of physiologic resorption, and many pulpally involved teeth have no mobility.

Electric pulp tests are not valid in primary teeth.⁷ Laser Doppler flowmetry might be of greater help in determining vitality, but this equipment has not been perfected, and the price is prohibitive.⁸ Thermal tests are usually not conducted on primary teeth because of their reliability.⁷

After the clinical examination, radiographs of good quality are essential. Like permanent teeth, periapical radiolucencies appear at the apices in primary anterior teeth. In primary molars, pathologic changes most often apparent in the bifurcation or trifurcation areas. Consequently, bite-wing radiographs are often best to observe pathologic changes in posterior primary teeth. Pathologic bone and root resorptions are signs of advanced pulpal pathosis that has spread into the periapical tissues and is usually treatable only with extraction.

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Surgical Exposure of Impacted Upper Incisor and its Proper Alignment in the Dental Arch

RMG Rabbani¹, AK Saha², RP Biswas³, MSA Khan⁴, KNC Fansé⁵, MZ Hossain⁶

Abstract

Surgical exposure of impacted upper incisor is very complex. So fixed orthodontic treatment rehabilitation is the first choice of treatment for correction of malocclusion. A clinical case report of a 10-year old boy with an un-erupted mal-posed upper left central incisor was treated by sequential surgical exposure and fixed orthodontic treatment. The tooth was aligned in the dental arch with accepted aesthetic and functional satisfaction of the patient.

Key Words: impacted tooth, surgical exposure, fixed orthodontics

Introduction

Permanent tooth eruption failure can create orthodontic problem. A localized problem is typically created by displacement of a permanent tooth from its normal eruption path so that the tooth becomes impacted and maxillary canine is mostly affected¹. Impaction of upper central incisor is not a common problem for the orthodontist. This type of case can be managed by both surgical and orthodontic approaches^{2,3,4}. The patient presented in this case report, exhibited a challenging and difficult impaction of left upper central incisor, the correction of which required orthodontic traction of impacted tooth after being surgically exposed. The patient was treated by surgical exposure of upper left central incisor immediately slanted edgewise fixed appliance was fitted and then in orthodontic way brought into the dental arch with proper alignment.

History and Clinical Examination:

A 10-year old boy reported to the department of

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5. Dr. Kamrun Nahar Chowdhury Fansé, BDS, Department of PH & HA, NIPSOM, Dhaka.
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Orthodontics, Dhaka Dental College and Hospital with the complaint of failure of eruption of a tooth in his jaw as his chief complaint. Patient's mother was aware of this problem and wanted proper treatment even with the aid of surgery. The patient had a straight profile with competent lip and good facial symmetry. An Angle Class I malocclusion with impacted upper left central incisor was noted (Fig. 2). Clinical assessment of mandibular closure from rest position to habitual occlusion showed no mandibular displacement. Panoramic radiography revealed the presence of all permanent teeth with impacted (labio-version) upper left central incisor. No sign or symptom of TMJ pathology was noted.

Treatment Objectives

Study model, clinical feature and panoramic radiography revealed the need of the following treatment objectives:-

1. Surgical exposure of upper left central incisor and
2. Proper alignment of teeth for aesthetic purpose and prevention of further development of any pathological lesion.

Treatment Plan and Progress

The patient was treated in three phases, (1) surgical exposure, (2) attachment to the tooth and (3) orthodontic mechanics to bring the tooth into the arch. First the tooth was exposed surgically by reflecting the flap of the crest of the alveolus and sutured so that attached gingival has been transferred to the region where the crown is exposed and waited for two to three weeks for spontaneous eruption. The tooth projected towards the upper lip. Then palatal button was bonded on the palatal surface of the tooth. The standard edgewise fixed appliance was set in the upper arch and traction from the central incisor was given for downward movement of tooth. After the movement, bracket was set on the labial surface of tooth and

Surgical exposure of impacted

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treatment completed (Fig.3).

Results

One year after the initial treatment, the patient was consulted again with pre and post treatment records. A Class I incisor relation was achieved with optimal

Pre-Treatment Radiograph

Pic-01

Pic-02

Pic-03

Pic-04

Pic-05

Pic-06

After Treatment Photograph

Pic-I

Pic-II

Pic-III

overbite and over jet relationship (Fig.ii). The post treatment panoramic radiography revealed a complete eruption of upper left central incisor. The root of the tooth was fairly parallel, supporting tissue appeared healthy clinically and radiologically.

Discussion

Proper treatment of this case showed improvement of aesthetics and prevention of development of any pathological condition. The relationship of both dentitions improved. However, there was a risk of damage to tooth during surgical exposure as the tooth was several times impacted. Alternate option was surgical transplantation. External root resorption often ensues after transplantation and is the major failure^{5,6,7}. But use of fixed appliance with controlled movement of tooth helped the patient to a more improved functional dental and aesthetic relationship. To enhance the long-term stability of the result, the fixed appliance should be kept in place up to eruption of permanent canine. Timely and proper orthodontic treatments with the cooperation of the patient are instrumental in the success of treatment⁶.

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